

DELIVERABLE

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D2.2.3 Metadata Mappings

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0.2	31/10/10	Vassilis Tzouvaras, Nasos Drosopoulos	NTUA	Integration of comments from Kate Fernie (MDR) and Christian Ertmann-Christiansen (KUAS)
0.3	06/12/10	Vassilis Tzouvaras, Despoina Trivela, Eleni Tsalapati, Nasos Drosopoulos	NTUA	Integration of metadata crosswalks
0.3	17/12/10	Christos Papatheodorou, Constantia Kakali, Giannis Tsakonas	DCU	EDM crosswalk
0.4	22/12/10	Vassilis Tzouvaras, Nasos Drosopoulos	NTUA	Final draft including metadata crosswalks
0.5	31/1/11	Vassilis Tzouvaras, Nasos Drosopoulos	NTUA	Final version integrating peer review comments on the metadata crosswalks
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Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on the results of Task 3 (Metadata and vocabularies) of WP2 (Preparing and enabling) concerning crosswalks for the CARARE metadata schema¹. Its main objective is to provide the CARARE ingestion system with the information and technical specifications for the transformation of provider's metadata to the CARARE schema and, for the interoperability of the later with the Europeana repository and relevant standardized and widely used data models for digital cultural heritage.

The results of this task are also based upon the efforts and contributions of the members of the CARARE metadata working group, the DCU metadata team and the English Heritage Data Standards Unit including: Christos Papatheodorou, Christian Ertmann-Christiansen, Kate Fernie, Maria Emilia Masci, Oliver Mamo, Börje Justrell, Sven Ole Clemens, Vassilis Tzouvaras, Dimitris Gavrilis, Stavros Angelis, Constantia Kakali, Giannis Tsakonas, Panos Constantopoulos, Costis Dallas, Sólborg Una Pálsdóttir, Effie Patsatzi, Lena Inger Larsen, Daniel Pletinckx, Nasos Drosopoulos, Vykintas Vaitkevičius, Rimvydas Laužikas, Phil Carlisle, Gillian Grayson and Stephen Stead.

The deliverable is structured as follows:

- *Introduction:* Explaining the context of the work package and the objectives of the task that the deliverable relates with, the application of the results in the project's following tasks and, the basic concepts the reader should grasp to have a good understanding of the deliverable content.
- *The CARARE schema:* A brief overview of the schema. The schema outline, xsd implementation are published on the project website at <http://www.carare.eu/eng/Resources/> and are provided in separate files for inclusion in this deliverable.
- *The CARARE schema crosswalks:* Report on established metadata mappings between CARARE schema and identified models. Due to their size and nature, the crosswalk tables are provided in separate files for inclusion in this deliverable and for subsequent publication on <http://www.carare.eu/eng/Resources/>.
- *Mapping providers' metadata:* An overview of the procedure and tool that will be deployed within CARARE, in order to establish interoperability between provider's metadata and the CARARE schema.

¹ [CARARE metadata schema outline, v1.0](#)

1. Introduction

Metadata, literally “data about data”, provide a wide variety of information describing a resource, such as the subject matter and its creators, technical information to store and access the resource, legal rights, etc. Metadata records are critical to the documentation and maintenance of interrelationships between information resources and are being used to find, gather, and maintain resources over long periods of time. The consistent application of a descriptive metadata standard improves the user's search experience and makes information retrieval within a single collection or across multiple collections more reliable. Administrative, technical, and preservation metadata contribute to the management of information resources and help to ensure their intellectual integrity both now and in the future².

In parallel with other domains, many researchers in the digital cultural heritage community recognize the need to lower the barriers for the management and aggregation of digital resources, by implementing some measure of interoperability among metadata standards and then with proprietary data structures. There is a wide range of proposed solutions, including crosswalks, translation algorithms, metadata registries, and specialized data dictionaries. One definition of interoperability is "the ability of different types of computers, networks, operating systems, and applications to work together effectively, without prior communication, in order to exchange information in a useful and meaningful manner. Interoperability can be seen as having three aspects: semantic, structural and syntactic."³ Semantic mapping is the process of analyzing the definitions of the elements or fields to determine whether they have the same or similar meanings. Structural interoperability refers to the presence of data models or wrappers that specify the semantic schema being used. Syntactic interoperability, also called technical interoperability, refers to the ability to communicate, transport, store, and represent metadata and other types of information between and among different systems and schemas.⁴

A crosswalk provides a mapping of metadata elements from one metadata standard to another. The prerequisite to a meaningful mapping requires a clear and precise definition of the elements in each standard. The primary difficulty is to identify the common elements in different metadata schemas and put this information to use in systems that resolve differences between incompatible records. Crosswalks are typically presented as tables of equivalent elements in two standards and, even though the equivalences may be inexact, they represent an expert's judgment that the conceptual differences are immaterial to the successful operation of a software process that involves records encoded in the two standards⁵. A crosswalk supports the ability of a retrieval mechanism to query fields with the same or similar content in different data sources; in other words, it supports semantic interoperability. Crosswalks are not only important for supporting the demand for single point of access or cross-domain searching; they are also instrumental for converting data from one format to another. However, aggregating metadata records from different repositories may create confusing display results, especially if some of the metadata are automatically generated or created without following best practices or using standard thesauri and controlled vocabularies. Mapping metadata

² [Metadata Advisory Group of the MIT Libraries](#)

³ [DCMI Glossary](#)

⁴ [Introduction to metadata – T. Gill et al.](#)

⁵ [OCLC – Online Computer Library Center](#)

elements from different schemas is only one level of crosswalking. At another level of semantic interoperability are the data content standards for formulating the data values that populate the metadata elements, for example, rules for recording personal names or encoding standards for dates.

The process of metadata mappings in CARARE supports subsequent critical activities:

- migrating from providers' legacy schemas (whether standard or local) to CARARE,
- harvesting or aggregating metadata records that were created using shared community standard or different metadata standards and,
- transforming records from CARARE schema to another, particularly Europeana Semantic Elements and Europeana Data Model.

2. The CARARE Schema

The CARARE Metadata Working Group held its first meeting in Athens on 8–9th April to evaluate the relevant metadata schemas for the heritage domain and to identify the schema for the CARARE project to use to mediate between content provider's native data and the data models implemented by Europeana.

The Group identified five metadata schemas as being of particular relevance to the CARARE project; the rdf implementation of the CIDOC CRM, LIDO, MIDAS Heritage, a Greek DTD implementation of CIDOC and the Europeana Data Model (EDM) itself. The working group then analysed these schemas in two main ways: Test mappings were completed by members of the group between the data in their native systems and the identified schemas. Comparative crosswalks were provided between three major schemas (MIDAS, LIDO and POLIS) by the DCU team. Following this analysis a SWOT analysis was undertaken to identify the advantages and disadvantages of the different schemas, looking in particular at concepts such as 'time' and 'space'.

In recommending the development of a metadata schema for the CARARE project, the working group took into consideration the strengths of the MIDAS schema with respect to geographic information and of the LIDO schema with respect to digital resources.

The CARARE metadata schema⁶ is implemented as a harvesting XML schema intended for delivering metadata to the CARARE service environment about an organisation's online collections, monument inventory database and digital objects. It has been established by the project to ensure interoperability between the native metadata held by heritage organisations and the standards and schemas defined by Europeana.

The CARARE metadata schema builds on existing standards and best practice from a number of different countries in Europe and the rest of the world including MIDAS Heritage (the English Heritage standard), POLIS (an application profile of the CIDOC CRM established by a Greek national project), LIDO (the harvesting schema developed by CIDOC's Data Harvesting and Interchange Working Group in cooperation with the eContentplus ATHENA project), the CIDOC

⁶ [CARARE v1.0. XSD](#)

archaeological sites core data index, the Council of Europe's Core Data Index to Historic Buildings and Monuments of the Architectural Heritage and the INSPIRE directive for Geographic Information.

In the framework of CARARE metadata working group, MIDAS Heritage, LIDO, Dublin Core, Europeana Semantic Elements and Europeana Data Model have been identified and analysed in order to develop crosswalks with the CARARE schema. The work was aimed at providing crosswalks between both the published schema and their XSD. Implementation of the later will ensure the crosswalks' integration as templates in the metadata mapping tool, both to facilitate the ingestion of metadata which conforms to widely used schema such as MIDAS or LIDO - and also to facilitate transformation into Europeana's metadata format.

For the metadata schema outline, please see the file entitled CARARE metadata schema outline v1.pdf.

For the metadata XSD, please see the file entitled CARARE v1.0.xsd.

3. The CARARE schema crosswalks

This section introduces the CARARE schema crosswalks. Each crosswalk is presented in a linked document published in a series on the project website at <http://www.carare.eu/eng/Resources>.

3.1 MIDAS Heritage crosswalk

MIDAS Heritage⁷ is the UK data standard for information about the historic environment, developed for and on behalf of the Forum on Information Standards in Heritage (FISH). MIDAS XML is part of the FISH interoperability tool-kit used to enable data exchange between regional heritage inventories and the national heritage portal in the UK. MIDAS is closely related to the CARARE schema both conceptually and technically, in the way they address annotation of monuments.

The full crosswalk between MIDAS Heritage and CARARE is presented in the file titled “carare_d2.2.3_3.1”

3.2 Lightweight Information Describing Objects (LIDO)

LIDO⁸ widely addresses contribution of content to cultural heritage repositories and was developed through the increasing relevance and necessity of internet presence for museums and other collections. It is the result of a joint effort of the CDWA Lite⁹, museumdat¹⁰, SPECTRUM¹¹ and CIDOC CRM¹² communities. The schema combines the CDWA Lite and museumdat schemas and is informed by SPECTRUM. Being CIDOC-CRM compliant, it aims at contributing information of all kinds of museum objects for resource discovery. Due to the relation and need of association between museum objects and monument sites and based on the common field of application for LIDO and CARARE.

The full crosswalk between LIDO and the CARARE schemas is presented in the file titled “carare_d2.2.3_3.2”

3.3 Dublin Core (DC) and Europeana Semantic Elements (ESE)

The Dublin Core Metadata Initiative¹³ has addressed the proliferation of metadata formats by providing a framework for designing application profiles that meet specific application needs, while providing semantic interoperability with other applications on the basis of globally defined vocabularies and models. It is commonly used across cultural heritage institutions and is considered the minimum level of interoperability between them, especially in the framework of Europeana. The

⁷ <http://www.english-heritage.org.uk/professional/archives-and-collections/nmr/heritage-data/midas-heritage/>

⁸ <http://www.lido-schema.org>

⁹ http://getty.art.museum/research/conducting_research/standards/cdwa/cdwalite.html

¹⁰ <http://www.museumdat.org/index.php?ln=en>

¹¹ <http://www.collectionstrust.org.uk/spectrum>

¹² <http://www.cidoc-crm.org/>

¹³ <http://www.dublincore.org/>

ESE¹⁴ v3.3 XML Schema extends the DC XML Schema with the addition of elements belonging to the Europeana namespace.

The crosswalk between the CARARE schema and DC is presented in the file titled “carare_d2.2.3_3.3”

3.4 Europeana Data Model (EDM)

The Europeana Data Model¹⁵ is developed as an integration medium for collecting, connecting and enriching the descriptions provided by Europeana content providers. It is regarded as a qualitative change in the way Europeana deals with the metadata gathered from data providers and aggregators, aiming to solve some of the issues observed with the current ESE, by providing additional expressivity and flexibility. EDM is not built on any particular community standard but rather adopts an open, cross-domain Semantic Web-based framework that can accommodate particular community standards such as LIDO, EAD or METS. Since CARARE is an aggregation project for Europeana, the crosswalk to EDM is of particular importance.

The crosswalk between the CARARE schema and the EDM is presented in the file titled “carare_d2.2.3_3.4”

¹⁴ [Europeana Semantic Elements Specification v3.3](#)

¹⁵ [Europeana Data Model Definition v.5.2](#)

4. Mapping providers' metadata to the CARARE schema

4.1 CARARE Aggregation

CARARE will setup a platform to offer services for content providers in order to perform ingestion and aggregation of resources, leveraging the expertise and available resources regarding metadata crosswalks. Due to the nature of a European thematic aggregation there is an expected diversity among participating providers and content. The software tools need to accommodate inexperienced users and legacy data, while taking advantage of the domain experts' knowledge and the project's working groups' results. The crosswalks that are delivered in present document will be implemented and integrated to manage the translation of different metadata standards. A tool for visually mapping local metadata schemas to the CARARE one will ensure the success of a large scale aggregation by providing an intuitive, user-friendly approach that reduces the effort to create translation logic for mappings and the turnaround time between human-readable crosswalks and executable code.

4.2 Ingestion workflow

CARARE project's ingestion procedure illustrated in Fig. 1, consists of four phases, each responsible for specific services required in order to ensure the effectiveness and quality of the aggregation.

Figure 1. Ingestion workflow

Harvesting/delivery is the process responsible for collecting the metadata from distributed repositories. It will be an interface for different methods of data delivery such as HTTP or FTP upload and OAI-PMH.

Semantic Mapping will provide the service for assigning semantics to the harvested metadata. A mapping tool will assist providers to manually align their local schemas to the reference data model. Providers that have metadata in supported known formats might be able to omit this step by using stored transformations from selected schemas to the reference schema based on existing crosswalks.

Value Mapping ensures the correct formulation of values for controlled metadata fields. It will enable providers to resolve data issues, e.g. map own terminology list to selected terminology lists and to automate data normalization according to selected vocabularies and best practices for values such as dates, geographical locations, nationality/language, etc.

Revision/Annotation will enable the revision of the transformation results as well as the editing or addition of data that is not in the original metadata (e.g. empty fields or, ones that take values from controlled vocabularies).

Across the four phases, a set of tools for **Analysis & Statistics** provides detailed information on the metadata contributed by a provider (i.e. number of items imported, total values per field etc), while **Quality Control** procedures will automatically check and report on ingested metadata (i.e. missing values, malformed data).

4.3 CARARE Mapping Tool

The CARARE metadata mapping tool is based on MINT¹⁶, the tool developed by NTUA and implemented in a number of Europeana content delivery projects including Athena and EU Screen. This service formalizes the notion of crosswalk by hiding technical details and permitting the semantic equivalences to emerge as the centrepiece. As a result, content providers and domain experts, who are typically not programmers, can easily enter the translation logic that can be automatically converted into executable code. It involves a graphical environment where a user attempts to achieve interoperability by mapping one pair of elements (local and CARARE schema) at a time. A user import is not required to include the schema used in order to simplify the actual work for the user by reducing the set of elements that have to be mapped to only those that are populated and, to avoid inconsistencies between schema declaration and actual usage. The Schema Generator module produces the required simplified version of the schema that corresponds to a specific import by the user. This structure is visualized in the mapping interface as an interactive tree that represents a snapshot of the XML schema that the user is going to use as input for the mapping process. The Mapping Interface is responsible for creating and presenting an intuitive and visual appealing environment for the user to define mappings, without sacrificing any of the functionality needed to properly achieve the task of schema mapping (e.g conditional mappings, string manipulation functions etc.).

¹⁶ <http://mint.image.ntua.gr>

Define your mappings and when you are done click the 'Finished' button below to make them available to the rest of the users in your organization.
*Mapping relations are automatically saved every time you edit, delete or create a new one.

Finished Preview Summary

Source Schema

- [-] museumdatWrap
 - [+] @schemaLocation
 - [+] @langencoding
 - [+] @lang
 - [-] museumdat
 - [+] descriptiveMetadata
 - [+] objectClassificationWrap
 - [-] identificationWrap
 - [+] titleWrap
 - [-] titleSet
 - [+] title
 - [+] repositoryWrap
 - [+] descriptionWrap
 - [+] eventWrap
 - [+] relationWrap
 - [+] administrativeMetadata

Mappings

heritagAsset:	structural	
recordInformation:		?
appellation:		?
description:	unmapped	@ ?
actors:		?
designations:		?
conditions:		?
characters:		?
references:		?
relations:		?

Target Schema

- Collection Information
- Heritage Assets
- Digital Resources
- Activities

Figure 2. Screenshot of the mapping tool

Finished Preview Summary

Source Schema

- [-] museumdatWrap
 - [+] @schemaLocation
 - [+] @langencoding
 - [+] @lang
 - [-] museumdat
 - [+] descriptiveMetadata
 - [+] objectClassificationWrap
 - [+] identificationWrap
 - [+] descriptionWrap
 - [+] displayCreator
 - [+] displayCreationDate
 - [+] displayCreationLocation
 - [+] displayMeasurements
 - [+] displayMaterialsTech
 - [+] descriptiveNoteWrap
 - [+] displayEventWrap
 - [+] eventWrap
 - [+] relationWrap
 - [+] administrativeMetadata

Mappings

title:	
keywords:	
contacts:	
rights:	
source:	
language:	
statement:	
creation:	
createdOn:	
query:	
coverage:	
spatialReferen	

Help

Namespace: museumdat
Name: displayCreationDate
Count: 210
Distinct Count: 78

Value	Frequency
1896	14
1920	13
2. Hälfte 18. Jahrhundert	12
2. Viertel 19. Jahrhundert	11
1900 [circa]	10
1955 [circa]	9
1740 [circa]	9
1930 [circa]	8
1904	7
1960 [circa]	6
1910 [circa]	6
Anfang 20. Jahrhundert	5

Target Schema

- Collection Information
- Heritage Assets
- Digital Resources
- Activities

Figure 3. Statistics for an input element

In order to offer a more user friendly environment to perform the task of schema mapping, the tool can be configured to provide to the user with groups of high level elements that constitute separate semantic entities. These top level sets of elements are presented on the right side of the mapping Interface as can be seen in Figure 2. Clicking the corresponding button, the set of the sub-elements

that are part of that group are presented to him in the middle part of the screen. This part of the user interface has a tree structure of embedded boxes that represents the internal structure of the complex element. The user is able to interact with this structure by clicking to collapse and expand it, similar to what he is able to do the with the tree representation of the input schema. Every embedded box represents an element and the user is able to request and view any information about it that is part of the XML schema. On the left side of the user interface a tree structure represents the schema produced for a specific import. The user is able to navigate the tree and access element statistics for the specific import, e.g. see Figure 3. When a user wants to perform an actual mapping between the input and the target schema, he has to drag and drop any element he wishes from the tree structure on the left part of the user interface to one of the boxes in the middle. When a successful mapping occurs, the user gets notified for the event and he is able to view the mappings in the middle part of the screen.

The user interface of the mapping tool is completely schema aware regarding the target schema. That means that many operations might be restricted based on constraints that appear in the target XML schema. For example, if an element can be repeated the user is able by using a button that appears on the visual representation of that element to add another one and make a new mapping. User's mapping actions are expressed through XSLT¹⁷ stylesheets, i.e. a well-formed XML document conforming to the Namespaces in XML Recommendation. XSLT stylesheets are stored and can be applied to any user data, can be exported and published as a well-defined, machine understandable crosswalk and, shared with other users to act as template for their mapping needs.

¹⁷ <http://www.w3.org/TR/xslt>

5. Conclusions

The process of carrying out metadata crosswalks is an ongoing process for the CARARE project.

Additional crosswalks to widely used standard schemas such as CDWA Lite are under consideration and may be completed if such schemas are in use by content organisations planning to provide their metadata for ingestion to the CARARE repository. The

The crosswalk between the CARARE schema and the EDM will be reviewed and may be refined as Europeana implements the EDM in its user interfaces, or in the event of any changes or developments to the EDM schema itself.

6. References

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The CARARE metadata schema

Christos Papatheodorou, Phil Carlisle, Christian Ertmann-Christiansen and Kate Fernie

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Revision History

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0.1	4/6/10	Christos Papatheodorou, Stavros Angelis, Dimitris Gavrilis, Constantia Kakali, Giannis Tsakonas, Panos Constantopoulos, Costis Dallas	DCU	Report on evaluation of metadata schemas and mappings to the CIDOC CRM and outline schema
0.2	8/7/10	Phil Carlisle	English Heritage	Mappings of MIDAS Heritage to the CIDOC CRM and MIDAS Lite schema
0.3	13/7/10	K Fernie	MDR Partners	Draft
0.4	20/7/10	C Ertmann-Christiansen & K Fernie	KUAS & MDR	Revised draft
0.5	21/7/10	K Fernie	MDR	Revised draft
0.6	29/7/10	Christos Papatheodorou	DCU	Revised draft
0.7	30/7/10	C Ertmann-Christiansen	KUAS	Revised draft
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0.10	12/8/10	Christos Papatheodorou & Christian Ertmann-Christiansen	DCU & KUAS	Revised draft
0.11	17/8/10	Christos Papatheodorou, Kate Fernie, Phil Carlisle & Christian Ertmann-Christiansen	DCU, MDR, EH, KUAS	Revised draft
0.12	22/9/10	Christian Ertmann-Christiansen	KUAS	Revised draft based on comments following review by Stuart Jeffrey, Antoine Isaac, Franc Zakrajsek,

				Anestis Koutsoudis, Daniel Pletinckx
0.13	30/9/10	Christos Papatheodorou	DCU	Cardinality and minor corrections.
0.14	1/10/10	Christos Papatheodorou, Kate Fernie, Costis Dallas, Dimitris Gavrilis, Christian Ertmann-Christiansen	DCU, MDR, KUAS	Draft for general review.
1.0.0	1/11/10	Kate Fernie & Christian Ertmann-Christiansen	KUAS	Version 1 for implementation following general review.

1. Introduction

One of CARARE's main objectives is to ensure interoperability between the native metadata held by heritage organisations and the metadata used by Europeana. The project is establishing a metadata schema which will be used to mediate between the original data and the standards and schemas defined by Europeana.

The proposed schema builds on existing standards and best practice from a number of different countries in Europe and the rest of the world including:

CIDOC Archaeological Sites Core Data Index

The Archaeological Sites Core Data Index was established by an international working group with the aim of facilitating communications between the national and international bodies responsible for the archaeological heritage, to assist the development of record systems and to facilitate research using archaeological site data.

Core Data Index to Historic Buildings and Monuments of the Architectural Heritage

Core Data Index as the "Recommendation on the co-ordination of documentation methods and systems related to historic buildings and monuments of the architectural heritage" was adopted by the Committee of Ministers of the Council of Europe on 11 January 1995. The basic aim of the Core Data Index is to make it possible to classify individual buildings and sites by name, location, functional type, date, architect or patron, building materials and techniques, physical condition, and protection status. It is not an end in itself, but a starting point to further information held in databases, documentation centres, and elsewhere that is necessary for the detailed understanding and care of individual monuments.

CIDOC CRM

The CIDOC Conceptual Reference Model (CIDOC CRM) is the result of over 10 years work by the CIDOC Documentation Standards Working Group and CIDOC CRM Special Interest Group, and is an ISO standard (ISO 21127 (2005)).

The CIDOC CRM is a formal standard that defines documentation concepts for the cultural heritage and the relationships between those concepts. It provides a flexible standard framework that cultural heritage data can be mapped to and provides a framework for semantic interoperability.

MIDAS Heritage

MIDAS Heritage is a data standard for information about the historic environment which was developed by English Heritage in collaboration with the UK Forum for Information Standards in Heritage and a number of heritage organisations in the UK building on the CIDOC Archaeological Sites Core Data Index and the CIDOC CRM. MIDAS Heritage covers the three main themes:

- **Heritage assets** – buildings, archaeological monuments, landscape areas, shipwreck sites, find-spots, artefacts and ecofacts.
- **Activities** – Field investigation, Research and Analysis, Management Activity, Casework and Consultation, Designation and Protection and also Historical events.
- **Information sources** – bibliographic sources, archive materials, management documentation, and narratives and syntheses (e.g. text plus images for educational purposes).

and the following supporting information:

- **Spatial information** – Location and map information

- **Temporal information** – Date and period
- **Actor information** – people, organisations and their roles

POLIS DTD

The POLIS DTD was produced as part of an EU funded Greek national research project to develop an interoperability framework for the cultural heritage. A series of DTDs were produced for different applications (including monument inventories, museums, archives, bibliographies etc) each derived from the CIDOC CRM. The Monument Inventory DTD was closely related to the core data index for archaeological sites.

LIDO

LIDO – Lightweight Information Describing Objects is a metadata harvesting schema developed by the ATHENA Project for harvesting museum data into the service environment of Europeana. LIDO is based on CDWA Lite, MuseumDat, the CIDOC CRM and SPECTRUM. LIDO is made up of a nested set of ‘wrapper’ and ‘set’ elements which structure records and contain ‘data elements’ which hold the information that is being harvested and delivered to the user of the service environment. There are 7 areas in a LIDO record for an object:

- Object identification
- Object classification
- Relations of the object
- Events – in which the object has taken part
- Rights work – information about the rights associated with the object, metadata and digital surrogate
- Record – basic information about the record
- Resource – information about the resource being supplied to the service environment (Europeana)

GIS (Geographic Information System) metadata

MIDAS Heritage complies with the UK GEMINI Discovery Metadata Standard, which specifies a set of metadata elements for describing geographic datasets (which is used by the UK’s GIGateway™ metadata service run by the Association for Geographic Information). English Heritage has work underway to implement the INSPIRE directive for GIS metadata before the end of 2010.

ISO 8601

All dates in the CARARE schema conform with ISO 8601, i.e. they are specified largest temporal term first and according to the Gregorian calendar; e.g. 1981-04-05.

The CARARE schema builds on these standards and also the work of the members of the CARARE metadata working group, the DCU metadata team and the English Heritage Data Standards Unit including: Maria Emilia Masci, Oliver Mamo, Börje Justrell, Sven Ole Clemens, Vassilis Tzouvaras, Dimitris Gavrilis, Stavros Angelis, Constantia Kakali, Giannis Tsakonas, Panos Constantopoulos, Costis Dallas, Sólborg Una Pálsdóttir, Effie Patsatzi, Lena Inger Larsen, Daniel Pletinckx, Nasos Drosopoulos, Vykintas Vaitkevičius, Rimvydas Laužikas, Phil Carlisle, Gillian Grayson and Stephen Stead.

2. Outline of the CARARE schema

It is important to note that this is a harvesting schema intended for delivering metadata to the CARARE service environment of an organisation's online collections, monument inventory database and digital objects. It does not support activities such as monument management and protection. The strength of the schema lies with its ability to support the full range of descriptive information about monuments, building, landscape areas and their representations.

The schema is an application profile based on MIDAS Heritage and the POLIS DTD for monument inventories. MIDAS Heritage is a detailed standard intended for the full documentation of all aspects of heritage management not all of which are relevant to the CARARE service environment. The CARARE schema's focus is on the detailed description of monuments, events in which the monument has been involved and resources which represent and provide sources of information about the monument following the structure of the core data index for archaeological sites and the POLIS DTD enhanced by the expressiveness of LIDO.

The CARARE schema includes the LIDO Resource Set which covers the information needed for the digital resources being made accessible to the CARARE and Europeana service environment.

Conceptually the areas in a CARARE record for a monument are:

Heritage asset Identification – basic information about the monument, historic building, archaeological landscape area, shipwreck, artefact, ecofact etc.:

- Record information;
- Appellation (ID, name);
- Description
- Actors
- Designations
- Conditions
- Characters
 - Heritage asset type
 - Spatial (place, address, map coordinates)
 - Temporal (date, timespan, period)
 - Materials
 - Inscriptions
 - Dimensions
 - Craft
- Repository
- References
 - Record information - The ID, language, creation information and other metadata describing the record. The ID element of this information block holds the ID assigned by the content provider, cf. section 8.
 - Appellation (ID, name: the title of the reference)
 - Actor (the actor participating in the reference, except for the publisher; e.g. creator, archive, inventory organization, repository, compiler, etc.)
 - Type (archive, file, record, book, chapter, article etc.)
 - Medium
 - Extent
 - Rights

- Publication statement
- Subject
- Note
- Relations

Digital resource – these are digital resources (images, texts, videos, audio, 3D models) that provide sources of information about the monument being provided to the service environment (e.g. Europeana). They are often digital representations of monuments or of parts of monuments.

- Record information
- Appellation
- Actors
- Format
- Format Details
- Medium
- Extent
- Subject
- Spatial
- Temporal
- Publication statement
- Type
- Description
- Note
- Created
- Provenance
- Language
- Link
- IsShownAt
- Resource metadata location
- Relations
- Rights

Relations – relations of the monument, event or resource to other monuments, events, references or resources (see section 5):

- Type of relation
- Target of relation

Activity – events or activities that the monument has taken part in, such as: Creation, Field investigation; Research and analysis; Historical events, etc. For each event, information, if relevant, about:

- Record information;
- Appellation (ID, name);
- Description;
- Actors (persons and organisations);
- Event type;
- Temporal;
- Spatial;
- Assessments;
- Event method;
- Materials and techniques used;
- Relations

Record information – basic information about the record (see section 8):

- ID (the id in the provider's system) [mandatory];
- Type
- Source
- Creation – when created and who by;
 - Date
 - Actor
- Update – the date of the last update to the record and who by;
 - Date
 - Actor
- Language (of the metadata record)
- Rights
- Keywords

Rights – information about the rights associated with the object, metadata and the digital surrogate being harvested into the service environment (see section 9):

- Copyright
- Access rights
- Reproduction rights
- License

3. *Global wrappers*

The following elements define the top level elements of a CARARE:

CARARE – The CARARE schema start element. It wraps exactly one collection information wrapper and zero or more of each of the other global wrappers (Monument, Digital resource, Activity).

Collection information – holds the collection-level description.

Heritage asset – holds the metadata for a monument, including descriptive and administrative metadata.

Digital resource – holds the metadata about a digital resource.

Activity – holds the metadata about an event or activity.

Monuments, digital resources and activities are the “first-class” citizens of the CARARE schema. All other objects are hierarchically subsumed by them.

4. *Heritage Asset Identification Set*

The CARARE information set for heritage assets is based on the MIDAS Heritage standard, however the elements are compatible with the POLIS DTD and the CIDOC Core Data Index for Archaeological Sites.

The scope of this information set includes archaeological monuments, historic buildings, industrial monuments, archaeological landscape areas, shipwreck, artefacts and ecofacts. The ability to create relations between heritage asset records allows the relationships between individual monuments that form parts of a larger complex to be expressed, for example the Parthenon, Propylaea and the Erechtheum are part of the Acropolis of Athens.

Please note that global types are defined in section 11. The heritage asset information set includes:

Record information (source = MIDAS) (global) – The ID, language, creation information and other metadata describing the record. The ID element of this information block holds the ID assigned by the content provider, cf. section 8.

Appellation (global) – This is information about the identifier (ID) and name of the monument (see section 11). The ID sub-element is the record ID in the CARARE repository and will be generated by CARARE on ingest. The name sub-element may be repeated if a monument is known by more than one name, using the XML:lang attribute if the names are in alternate languages. A preferred/alternate attribute may be used to indicate which name is preferred.

Description (source = MIDAS) (global) – of the features of the archaeological monuments, historic buildings, industrial monuments, archaeological landscape areas, shipwreck, artefact or ecofact.

Actors (source = MIDAS) (global) – the actors involved with this monument, may be repeated.

Designations (source = MIDAS);

This is information about any designations for a monument or building which provide it with protection in law. There may be more than one designation.

- Protection type – the type of designation or protection.
- Grade – the grade or level of protection.
- Date from – the date from which the protection came into force.
- Date to – the date until which the monument is protected

Conditions (source = MIDAS);

This is information about the condition of a monument or building. The element is repeatable.

- Condition – the observed condition (e.g. good, fair, bad, poor, part destroyed, under restoration.)
- Condition Assessment - A detailed assessment of the condition of a Heritage Asset and any treatment required and an estimation of the percentage of the monument affected.
- Condition Date – the date when the assessment of condition was made.
- Relations – to an associated event/activity

Characters (source = MIDAS);

This is a set of index information to describe the character of the monument

- **Heritage asset type** (source = MIDAS) – classification of the monument, building, landscape feature, artefact or ecofact primarily with respect to its function or use, e.g. house. Use of a controlled vocabulary is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute. No particular common vocabulary is recommended for use.
 - Term
 - Namespace – this is the name/location of the controlled vocabulary from which the term is taken.
- **Temporal** (source = MIDAS) (Global) (see section 11)
- **Materials** (source = MIDAS) – the basic materials of which a monument is composed, e.g. brick, stone, tile. Use of a controlled vocabulary is

recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute. No particular common vocabulary is recommended for use.

- **Inscriptions** (source = MIDAS) – text inscribed on a monument or building, if any. The element may be repeated using the XML:lang attribute if the element value is available in alternate languages. A preferred/alternate attribute may be used to indicate which value is preferred. The type of inscription may be indicated using an attribute. Use of a controlled vocabulary to indicate the type of inscription is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute. No particular common vocabulary is recommended for use.
- **Dimensions** (source = MIDAS, LIDO)
 - **Measurement type** – e.g. height, length, width, depth, shape (e.g. oval)
 - **Units** – e.g. metres, centimetres
 - **Scale**
 - **Value**
- **Craft** (source = MIDAS) – this is a set of information to describe shipwrecks if any
 - Placeofregistration – of the ship
 - Nationality – of the ship
 - Constructionmethod – of the ship
 - Propulsion – of the ship
 - Lastjourneydetails – of the ship
 - Departure – Port of departure
 - Destination – Port of destination
 - Cargo – of the ship
 - Mannerofloss – how the ship was lost
 - Dateofloss – when the ship was lost
 - Dimensions – of the ship
 - Measurement type
 - Units
 - Scale
 - Value
- **Repository location** (source = LIDO) – identification of the institution with custody of the artefact and possibly the current location.

Spatial (source = MIDAS) (Global) (see section 11)

This is information about the place at which the heritage asset is located, included named places, postal address, the map coordinates and geometry of the heritage asset.

References – these are sources of information about the heritage asset in publications and archival sources (for example, photographs, drawings, plans, bibliographic references etc.). Do not include the digital objects (image, text, video, audio, 3D model, etc.) which your organisation is making accessible to Europeana – these should be described as Digital Resources, not References. Source = MIDAS + DCMI Terms. The information includes:

- **Record information** (source = MIDAS) (Global)
- **Appellation** – the ID and name given to the information source.
- **Actors** (source = MIDAS) (Global) – (creator, author, contributor, editor, etc.)
- **Type** (archive, file, record, book, chapter, article etc.) Use of a controlled vocabulary is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute. No particular common vocabulary is recommended for use.

- **Medium** (source = DCMI Terms) – the medium or physical carrier of the resource.
- **Extent** (source = DCMI Terms) – the size or extent of the resource
- **Subject** (source = DCMI Terms) – the topic of the resource. Use of a controlled vocabulary is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute. No particular common vocabulary is recommended for use.
- **Rights** (source = MIDAS)
- **Publication statement** (Global) (see section 11)
- **Note** (source = MIDAS) (Global)
- **Relations** – of the reference

Relations – of the heritage asset to other heritage assets, resources, events etc.

5. *Relations*

This is information about the relations between heritage assets, events or resources and other entities

- The type of relation, for example ‘is successor of’, ‘is next in sequence’, ‘has part’.
- The target of the relation (the ID number of the related heritage asset, event or resource)

The relations which are included in the Europeana Data Model are as follows:

- Is Derivative Of – a version of another resource
- Is Next In Sequence – the ordered parts of a resource, e.g. the pages in a book or an ordered sequence of 3D models showing the change of a monument over time.
- Is Related To – a general relationship between objects
- Is Representation Of – associates an information resource to the object that it represents, e.g. a digital image is a representation of the monument which is the target of the relation. We use it in the CARARE schema to associate a heritage asset and a Digital Resource
- Is Successor Of – the relation between the continuation of a resource and that resource, e.g. a church is successor of an earlier church on the same site.
- Occurred At – associates an event to the smallest known time span that overlaps with the occurrence of that event.
- Happened At – relates a place to the events which happened at that place.
- Was Present At – this relation associates the people, things or information sources with the Event that they were present at.
- Has Part – used for objects that incorporate other objects, e.g. a monument made up of smaller monuments or a site with a number of monuments.

Additional CARARE properties:

- hasEvent – associates a heritage asset with an Activity.
- Is Replica of – used for heritage assets that replicate other heritage assets, including scale models.
- Is In Front Of – a spatial relationship signifying the relative position of one monument to another.

- Is Behind – a spatial relationship signifying the relative position of one monument to another.
- Is Above – a spatial relationship signifying the relative position of one monument to another.
- Is Below – a spatial relationship signifying the relative position of one monument to another.
- Is North Of – a spatial relationship signifying the relative position of one monument to another.
- Is South Of – a spatial relationship signifying the relative position of one monument to another.
- Is East Of – a spatial relationship signifying the relative position of one monument to another.
- Is West Of – a spatial relationship signifying the relative position of one monument to another.
- Same As (source = OWL) – indicates that the two participants in the relation actually refer to the same thing.

6. *Digital Resource*

These are digital resources (image, text, video, audio, 3D model) that are being made accessible to the service environment (e.g. CARARE, Europeana). Use this to describe those digital objects which your organisation is making accessible to Europeana to represent a heritage asset (use Reference under Heritage Asset to describe other sources of information about the asset, e.g. bibliographic references or analogue representations of the object). Source = LIDO + MIDAS + DCMI Terms + Europeana Data Model.

The information set includes:

Record information (source = MIDAS) (Global) - The ID, language, creation information and other metadata describing the record. The ID element of this information block holds the ID assigned by the content provider, cf. section 8.

Appellation – the ID and the name given to the information source (see section 11).

Actors – The actors involved in the creation of a digital resource

Format (source = DCMI Terms) – the file format of the resource. Recommended best practice is to use a controlled vocabulary such as the list of Internet Media Types (MIME).

Format Details (source = DCMI Terms) – Additional information about the file or its production that could be of use in selecting an appropriate viewer for the resource, such as specific codecs used.

Medium (source = DCMI Terms) – the medium or physical carrier of the resource.

Extent (source = DCMI Terms) – the size or extent of the resource, including the unit of measurement.

Subject (source = DCMI Terms) – the topic of the resource. Use of a controlled vocabulary such as Getty Arts and Architecture thesaurus is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute.

Spatial (source = DCMI Terms) – the spatial characteristics of the digital resource (as opposed to the heritage asset it might represent).

Temporal (source = MIDAS) (Global) – use for dates associated with the topic of the resource, e.g. for digitised copies of historic photographs use for the date when the original photograph was taken (the date of the view of the monument) (see section 11).

Publication statement (see section 11)

Type (source = DCMI Terms) – The nature or genre of the resource. Use of the DCMI controlled vocabulary is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute.

Description (source = MIDAS) (Global) – The description of the resource, e.g. describe the view of the monument.

Note (source = MIDAS) (Global)

Created (source = DCMI Terms) – this is the date when the resource was created

Provenance (source = DCMI Terms) – A statement of any changes in ownership and custody of the resource since its creation that are significant for its authenticity, integrity, and interpretation.

Language (source = DC) – use for the language of the resource, e.g. the language sub-titles or a voice-over in a movie or a Virtual Reality model of a monument. Specified (like the

xml:lang attribute) using ISO 639-1:2002, i.e. standard two letter language codes (en, fr, etc.).

Link (source = LIDO) – the URL of the resource. A reference to the digital object on the content provider's web site in the best available resolution/quality (i.e. a link to the resource as a text, image, sound, or video file, **not** to the webpage that contains it). The data given here will allow the automatic generation of a thumbnail by Europeana for its functionality.

IsShownAt (source = ESE v3.3) – A URL to the digital object on the content provider's website in its full information context (i.e. a link to the webpage that contains the digital object and contextual information).

Resource metadata location (source = LIDO) – pointer to other information about the resource making the resource available

Relations – to heritage assets, other resources or to references.

Rights (source = MIDAS)

7. Activity

This is information about the events or activities that the monument has taken part in, for example: Field investigation; Research and analysis; Creation; Change in use; Historical events, etc. Source = MIDAS + POLIS DTD.

The information includes:

Record information (source = MIDAS) – The ID, language, creation information and other metadata describing the record. The ID element of this information block holds the ID assigned by the content provider, cf. section 8.

Appellation (source = MIDAS) (global) – This is the name of the event.

Description (source = MIDAS) (global) – of the event or activity which took place.

Actors (source = MIDAS) (global) – the people or organisations involved in this event, may be repeated.

Event type (source = MIDAS – classification of the type of event or activity which took place, e.g. survey, archaeological excavation, rebuilding. Use of a controlled vocabulary is recommended.

- Term
- Namespace – this is the name/location of the controlled vocabulary from which the term is taken.

Temporal (source = MIDAS) (Global) – the date or time span of the event.

Spatial (source = MIDAS) (Global) – the location or area covered by the event.

Assessments (source = MIDAS) – assessments made of the monument during the event, e.g. of the condition of the monument. Use of a controlled vocabulary is recommended.

- Term
- Namespace – this is the name/location of the controlled vocabulary from which the term is taken.

Event method (source = LIDO) – the method by which the event is carried out

Materials and techniques used (source = LIDO) – the materials and/or techniques used during the event. Use of a controlled vocabulary is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute. No particular common vocabulary is recommended for use.

Relations – of the event to other events, references, resources etc.

8. Record information

Basic administrative information about the record:

- ID – i.e. the local ID number in the content providers' information system; it is unique within the collection, but may follow any schema.
- Type – of the record. Use of a controlled vocabulary is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute. No particular common vocabulary is recommended for use.
- Source – of the record (the name of the organisation that maintains the record)
- Country – in which the head office of the organisation which maintains the record is based.
- Creation – when created and who by;
 - Actor
 - Date
- Update – the date of the last update to the record and who by;
 - Actor
 - Date
- Language (of the metadata record). Specifies the default language of the record; deviations in particular elements are specified using the xml:lang attribute where allowed. Specified (like the xml:lang attribute) using ISO 639-1:2002, i.e. standard two letter language codes (en, fr, etc.).
- Rights – to the metadata
- Keywords – for the record. CARARE will add general subject keywords such as archaeology, architecture or archaeological sites to each record. The element will be repeated using the XML:lang attribute to indicate the languages in which the keyword is available.

9. Rights

Information about the rights associated with the object, metadata and the digital surrogate being harvested into the service environment based on MIDAS Heritage. The information includes:

- Copyright
 - Rights holder;
 - Rights dates;
 - Credit line (statement)
- Access rights
 - Granted to
 - Conditions
 - Date from
 - Date to
 - Statement
- Reproduction rights
 - Statement
 - Contacts
 - Fees
- License – a URI indicating a license or conditions for the use of the object or data, e.g. a Creative Commons license¹ or the public domain mark². Use as an alternative or supplement to the information above.

¹ <http://creativecommons.org/about/licenses/>

² <http://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/mark/1.0/>

It is always recommended that the Copyright elements are given when known.

10. Collection information

The following elements provide a collection level description of the resources being harvested

- Title – the title of the collection. The element may be repeated using the XML:lang attribute if the element value is available in alternate languages. A preferred/alternate attribute may be used to indicate which value is preferred.
- Keywords – for the collection. The element may be repeated using the XML:lang attribute if the element value is available in alternate languages. Use of a controlled vocabulary such as Getty Arts and Architecture Thesaurus is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute.
- Contacts – for the collection
- Rights – associated with the collection as a whole
- Source – organisation that is the source of the collection
- Language – of the metadata. Specifies the default language of the records in the collection; deviations in particular records are specified in the record metadata, and deviations in particular elements are specified using the xml:lang attribute where allowed. Specified (like the xml:lang attribute) using ISO 639-1:2002, i.e. standard two letter language codes (en, fr, etc.).
- Statement – free text. The element may be repeated using the XML:lang attribute if the element value is available in alternate languages. A preferred/alternate attribute may be used to indicate which value is preferred.
- Creation – information about how the resources being harvested were collected includes:
 - Createdon – when the collection was created
 - Query - The query used to extract the data.
- Coverage – of the collection
 - Temporal – general temporal coverage of the collection
 - Spatial – general spatial coverage of the collection, e.g. the country covered.
- Spatial reference system – Use of a controlled vocabulary is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute. The OGC URN scheme for spatial reference systems is recommended for use.

11. Global types

The following types are used globally across the CARARE schema to define its elements.

Appellation (source = LIDO)

- ID – an identifier of an object. An attribute type should accompany this sub-element denoting the type of the identifier (URI, ISBN, etc.) The element may be repeated.
- Name – this is the name of the entity. The element may be repeated using the XML:lang attribute if the element value is available in alternate languages. A preferred/alternate attribute may be used to indicate which value is preferred.

Temporal (source = MIDAS).

Information about the date and/or period of an entity.

- Time span
 - start date – the earliest date in the range
 - end date – the latest date in the range
 - Dimension

- measurement unit – e.g. ‘years’
 - value – e.g. ‘474’
 - type – e.g. ‘AD’, ‘BCE’, ‘BPE’. Use of a controlled vocabulary is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute. No particular common vocabulary is recommended for use.
- Date range qualifier – the nature of the time span given (e.g. throughout, at some time during, etc.) Use of a controlled vocabulary is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute. No particular common vocabulary is recommended for use.
- Period name – the name given to the period in history when something occurred. The element may be repeated using the XML:lang attribute if the element value is available in alternate languages. A preferred/alternate attribute may be used to indicate which value is preferred.
- Display date – a free text field used to display the date or period for users (e.g. early 19th century, 1950s). The element may be repeated using the XML:lang attribute if the element value is available in alternate languages. A preferred/alternate attribute may be used to indicate which value is preferred.
- Scientific Date – date according to scientific dating methods, e.g. ‘1250 bp +/-30 PBN-1675’, recorded precisely as received from the specialist.
- Scientific Date Method – e.g. ‘radiocarbon dating’. Use of a controlled vocabulary is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute. No particular common vocabulary is recommended for use.

Spatial (source = MIDAS). Information about locations or positions in space.

- Location set
 - Named location – the name of a place or location which is relevant to the entity being described, for example ‘Lake Windermere’. The element may be repeated using the XML:lang attribute if the element value is available in alternate languages. A preferred/alternate attribute may be used to indicate which value is preferred. Use of a controlled vocabulary such as <http://www.geonames.org/> is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute.
 - Address – the postal address
 - Geopolitical area – the name of an administrative region which does not form part of the address, for example Scotland, England, Tuscany etc. May also be used for a historical geopolitical area, or an administrative unit (e.g. as defined in the INSPIRE directive).
 - Geopolitical area type. Use of a controlled vocabulary such as <http://www.geonames.org/> is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute.
 - Cadastral reference
 - Historical name. The element may be repeated using the XML:lang attribute if the element value is available in alternate languages. A preferred/alternate attribute may be used to indicate which value is preferred.
- Spatial reference system – Use of a controlled vocabulary is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute. The OGC URN scheme for spatial reference systems is recommended for use.
- Cartographic reference
 - Spatial feature type (how a feature is depicted in a GIS, e.g. point, line, polygon, multi-point, multi-line, multi-polygon). Use of a controlled vocabulary is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute. No particular common vocabulary is recommended for use.
 - Coordinates
 - X

- Y
 - Z
- Geometry
 - Bounding box
 - Min X
 - Min Y
 - Max X
 - Max Y
 - Quickpoint
 - X
 - Y
 - Entity: GML, Well-known text (WKT).
 - Stored precision, delivery precision (the precision of a coordinate as stored in the system, and as delivered to users).
 - Height: datum, units
 - Area: units
- Representations – how a feature is represented on a map

Address (source= MIDAS).

This is the postal address for a building, contact, etc.

- Building name
- Number in road – the number in a road or street used to identify a property
- Road name
- Town or city
- Postcode or zipcode
- Locality – a named area within which a monument or building lies
- Admin area – the name by which an administrative area is known, e.g. Shropshire
- Country

Actors (source = MIDAS + elements from LIDO).

- ID
- Name (the name of the person or organisation)
- ActorType (source = LIDO – indicates whether the actor is an individual, a group of individuals or an organisation.
- Roles – the roles of the actor (creator, custody, repository, curator, architect, sculptor, photographer, compiler, etc.) Use of a controlled vocabulary such as Getty Arts and Architecture thesaurus is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute.
- Contacts – contact information if known
- Vital dates (source = LIDO) – date of birth, date of death if known.
- Place of birth – Use of a controlled vocabulary such as <http://www.geonames.org/> is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute.
- Place of death – Use of a controlled vocabulary such as <http://www.geonames.org/> is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute.
- Place of activity – Use of a controlled vocabulary such as <http://www.geonames.org/> is recommended, and the vocabulary used may be indicated using an attribute.
- Biographical note – The element may be repeated using the XML:lang attribute if the element value is available in alternate languages. A preferred/alternate attribute may be used to indicate which value is preferred.

Contacts (source = MIDAS).

Information about how a person or organisation can be contacted

- Name – title, first name, last name, other name

- Role – the particular role played by the person or organisation
- Organisation
- Address – the postal address of the person or organisation
- Phone
- Fax
- Email

Description (source = MIDAS). The element may be repeated using the XML:lang attribute if the element value is available in alternate languages. A preferred/alternate attribute may be used to indicate which value is preferred.

- Full – a free text description of the entity
- Summary – a brief description of the entity

Publication statement

- Publisher
- Place – of publication
- Date – of publication

12. Elements Cardinality

The following table outlines the proposed schema and presents the cardinality of each element as well as defines if it is mandatory or not.

Element	Attribute	Mandatory/Repeatable
Carare		Y/N
Collection Information		Y/Y
Title		Y/Y
	xml:lang	Y/N
	preferred	N/N
Keywords		N/Y
	xml:lang	Y/N
Contacts		Y/Y
Rights		N/Y
Source		Y/N
Language		Y/Y Mandatory?
	xml:lang	Y/N
Statement		N/Y
	xml:lang	Y/N
	preferred	N/N
Creation		N/Y
	Createdon	N/Y
	Query	N/Y
Coverage		N/Y
	Temporal	N/Y
	Spatial	N/Y
Spatial reference system		Y/Y
	Preferred	N/N
Heritage asset Identification		Y/Y

	Record Information			Y/N
	Appellation			Y/Y
	Description			Y/N
	Actors			N/Y
	Designations			N/Y
		Protection type		Y/N
		Grade		N/N
		Date from		N/N
		Date to		N/N
	Conditions			N/Y
		Condition		N/N
		Condition Assessment		N/N
		Condition Date		N/N
		Relations		N/Y
	Characters			N/N
		Heritage asset type		Y/Y
			namespace	N/N
		Temporal		Y/Y to discuss ?
		Materials		N/Y
		Inscriptions		N/Y
			xml:lang	N/N
			type	N/N
			namespace	N/N
			preferred	N/N
		Dimensions		N/Y
		Craft		N/Y
	Repository location			N/Y
	Spatial			Y/Y to discuss ?
	References			N/Y
		Record information		Y/N
		Appellation		Y/Y
		Actors		Y/Y
		Type		Y/N
		Medium		N/N
		Extent		N/N
		Subject		N/Y
		Rights		N/Y
		Publication statement		Y/Y
		Note		N/N
		Relations		N/Y
	Relations			N/Y
Digital resource				N/Y
	Record information			Y/N
	Appellation			Y/Y
	Actors			N/Y
	Format			Y/Y

	Format Details			N/Y
	Medium			Y/Y
	Extent			Y/Y
	Spatial			N/Y
	Subject			N/Y
	Temporal			N/Y
	Publication statement			N/Y
	Type			Y/N
	Description			N/N
	Note			N/Y
	Created			N/N
	Provenance			N/N
	Language			N/Y
	Link			Y/N
	IsShownAt			N/N
	Resource metadata location			Y/N
	Relations			N/Y
	Rights			N/Y
			xml:lang	N/N
Relations				N/Y
	Appellation			Y/N
	Type of relation			Y/N
	Target of relation			Y/N
Activity				N/Y
	Record information			Y/N
	Appellation			Y/N
	Description			N/N
	Actors			N/Y
	Event type			Y/N
	Temporal			Y/Y
	Spatial			N/N
	Assessments			N/Y
			term	N/N
			namespace	N/N
	Event method			N/Y
	Materials and techniques			N/Y
	Relations			Y/Y
Record information				
	ID			Y/N
	Type			N/N
	Source			Y/N
	Country			Y/N
	Creation			
		Date		Y/N
		Actor		N/Y
	Update			
		Date		Y/N
		Actor		N/Y
	Language (of the			Y/Y

	metadata record)			
			xml:lang	N/N
	Rights			N/Y
	Keywords			N/Y
			xml:lang	Y/N
Rights				N/Y
	Copyright			N/Y
		Rights holder		N/Y
		Rights dates		N/Y
		Credit line (statement)		N/Y
	Access rights			N/Y
		Granted to		N/Y
		Conditions		N/Y
		Date from		N/N
		Date to		N/N
		Statement		N/Y
	Reproduction rights			N/Y
		Statement		N/Y
		Contacts		N/Y
		Fees		N/Y
	License			N/Y
Appellation				
	Name			Y/Y
			xml:lang	Y/N
	ID			Y/N
Dimensions				N/Y
	Measurement type			Y/N
	Units			Y/Y
	Scale			Y/Y ?
	Value			Y/Y
Craft				N/Y
	Placeofregistration			N/Y
	Nationality			N/N
	Constructionmethod			N/Y
	Propulsion			N/N
	Lastjourneydetails			N/N
		Departure		N/N
		Destination		N/Y
		Cargo		N/Y
		Mannerofloss		N/N
		Dateofloss		N/N
Temporal				
	Time span			N/Y
		start date		N/Y
		end date		N/Y
		Dimension		N/Y
		Date range qualifier		N/Y
			namespace	N/N
	Period name			N/Y
			xml:lang	Y/N
			preferred	N/N

	Display date			N/Y
			xml:lang	Y/N
			preferred	N/N
	Scientific Date			N/Y
	Scientific Date Method			N/Y
Spatial				
	Location set			Y/N
		Named location		N/Y
			xml:lang	Y/N
			preferred	N/N
			namespace	N/N
		Address		N/N
		Geopolitical area		N/N
		Geopolitical area type		N/N
			namespace	N/N
		Cadastral reference		N/N
		Historical name		N/Y
			xml:lang	Y/N
			preferred	N/N
	Spatial reference system			Y/N
	Cartographic reference			N/N
		Spatial feature type		Y/N
		Coordinates		Y/N
	Geometry			N/N
		Bounding box		N/N
		Quickpoint		N/N
		Entity		N/N
		Stored precision		N/N
		Height		N/N
		Area		N/N
	Representations			N/N
Coordinates				
	X			Y/N
	Y			Y/N
	Z			Y/N
Bounding Box				
	maxX			Y/N
	maxY			Y/N
	minx			Y/N
	minY			Y/N
Quickpoint				

	X			Y/N
	Y			Y/N
Address				Y/Y
	Building name			N/N
	Number in road			N/N
	Road name			N/N
	Town or city			Y/N
	Postcode or zipcode			N/N
	Locality			N/N
	Admin area			N/N
	Country			Y/N
Actors				
	ID			Y/N
	Name			Y/Y
	ActorType			Y/Y
	Roles			N/Y
			namespace	N/N
	Contacts			N/Y
	Vital dates			N/Y
			type	N/N
	Place of birth			N/Y
			namespace	N/N
	Place of death			N/Y
			namespace	N/N
	Place of activity			N/Y
			namespace	N/N
	Biographical note			N/Y
			xml:lang	Y/N
			preferred	N/N
Contacts				N/Y
	Name			N/Y
	Role			N/Y
	Organisation			N/Y
	Address			N/Y
	Phone			N/Y
	Fax			N/Y
	Email			N/Y
Description				
			xml:lang	Y/N
			preferred	N/N
			type (full, summary)	N/N
Publication statement				
	Publisher			Y/Y
	Place – of publication			N/Y
	Date			N/Y

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MIDAS – CARARE metadata mapping

Revision: [final]

Authors:

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0.2	22/01/11	K Fernie	MDR	Integrating comments from Rimvydas Laužikas

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MIDAS – CARARE metadata mapping

MIDAS Heritage is a data standard for information about the historic environment. It states what information should be recorded to support effective sharing and long-term preservation of the knowledge of the historic environment. It was developed by English Heritage **Error! Reference source not found.** in collaboration with the UK Forum for Information Standards in Heritage and a number of heritage organisations in the UK building on the CIDOC Archaeological Sites Core Data Index and the CIDOC CRM.

The first edition of MIDAS (1998) made ‘recommendations’ on the content of historic environment datasets. MIDAS Heritage introduces a more prescriptive approach, with specific standards to assess whether a dataset or information system is or is not compliant with the standard. The decision to do this has been taken in view of the improving technology for the sharing of data (e.g. the FISH Interoperability Toolkit), and also the professional requirement for more objective methods for assessing compliance. It must be stressed that the compliance approach adopted is adaptable. The Information Groups and compliance profile means that in effect MIDAS Heritage is a set of closely integrated data standards, rather than one single standard.

MIDAS Heritage Structure

The MIDAS Heritage data standard has a three-level structure. Working from the broadest to the most specific these are:

- Themes: the broadest level areas of interest to the historic environment community. These are set out below.
- Information Groups: these set the specific standard for what should be included in an entry covering a particular subject. They are thematic groupings of related Units of Information which together answer key questions about some aspect of the historic environment and its management
- Units of Information: the basic ‘facts’ or items that make up an entry.

Midas Heritage Themes

Themes can be used for convenient description of the principle focus of an information system or dataset. Most heritage sector information systems using the MIDAS Heritage standard will focus on one or more of the main themes of Heritage Asset, Activity and Information Sources. Where the text, tables and definitions in MIDAS Heritage refer to a theme name, then that reference should be taken to apply equally to all the Information Groups that make up that theme.

Main themes

The following are the principle themes of interest in heritage information recording as well as the Information Groups that make up that theme.

Heritage Asset: The Information Groups in this theme are the principal focus of study and investigation in the heritage sector. They are ‘what we want to know about’. In the first edition of MIDAS (1998) the focus was on Monuments (buildings, archaeological remains, wreck sites, find-spots, etc.). MIDAS Heritage reflects changing approaches to the study of material remains of the past. ‘Heritage Asset’ has been adopted as an appropriately inclusive heading to embrace landscape-scale areas at one end of the scale, and individual artefacts and ecofacts at the other. The description and recording of the character of these closely related assets remains a core function of inventories using the MIDAS Heritage standard. However,

each asset type requires slightly different treatment, reflecting the nature of the asset and professional practices employed in their understanding. Information Groups in this theme are:

- Area
- Monument
- Artefact and Ecofact

Activity: This theme covers things that have happened. However it can also include the recording of plans for future work. A structured record of events relating to a particular Heritage Asset can be used to give context and meaning to the records of heritage asset character. It provides information on ‘how we know what we know’ (Investigative Activity, Research and Analysis) or on how a particular Heritage Asset has been managed through time (Heritage Asset Management Activity, Casework and Consultation, Designation and Protection). Historical events, not related to the investigation or recording of an asset, are also covered by MIDAS Heritage, as these may be recorded to provide explanatory context, for example for educational or outreach uses. Most information systems will only cover a few of these different activities. They are separated into distinct Information Groups to allow discussion of key issues and relationships relevant to each Activity. Information Groups within this theme are:

- Investigative Activity
- Designation and Protection
- Heritage Asset Management Activity
- Casework and Consultation
- Research and Analysis
- Historical Event

Information Sources: This theme covers traditional bibliographic references and references to primary archive materials, as well as online references. This is appropriate where the information is held outside an information system, for example in a publication, or on a web page. In this case the information system acts as a finding aid to point users to these further sources. Increasingly, however, additional information, for example text plus images, is being held within heritage information systems and may be deemed to be publications in their own right. This area is evolving as practice develops but two initial standards for this sort of content are included. Narrative and Synthesis covers education or instructional material integrated with the entries in an information system. Management Activity Documentation provides structured reports on aspects of the management of specific heritage assets. Information Groups included in this theme are:

- Archive and Bibliography
- Narrative and Synthesis
- Management Activity Documentation

Supporting themes

The following themes provide supplementary information to the main themes.

Spatial Information: Accurate knowledge of the position in space of Heritage Assets is central to their understanding and management. Similarly the location where events have

occurred, or to which Information Sources are relevant, is essential. Information Groups in this theme are:

- Location
- Map Depiction

Temporal Information: An understanding of the chronology of significant activities or events is common to all records of Heritage Assets. The standards presented here support recording of a wide variety of dates of different degrees of certainty, cultural periods and date ranges. These can either be derived from the physical aspects of the Heritage Asset itself (e.g. the style of a building) or from scientific investigation (e.g. radiocarbon dating) appropriate to recording the character of Heritage Assets. To avoid over-complication, where specific and undisputed ‘point in time’ dates are more appropriate, these are treated as separate units of information included in the appropriate Information Groups. The Information Group in this theme is:

- Date and Period

Actor Information: Heritage Assets were originally created by people, groups and cultures. The subsequent investigation, documentation, management and presentation of these assets are also the responsibility of organisations and individuals. The general term ‘actors’ is adopted by MIDAS Heritage, following usage in ISO 21127, for all the different organisations, groups, individuals documented in an information system. The information group in this theme is:

- Actor and Role

MIDAS XML

MIDAS XML is a set of W3C XML schemas established by the Forum for Information Standards in Heritage to provide a common format for the storage, processing and exchange of historic environment information in the UK. MIDAS XML covers all the information currently included in the MIDAS standard issued by FISH.

MIDAS – CARARE metadata mappings

Crosswalks have been completed between both [MIDAS Heritage](#) (the published data standard) and [MIDAS XML](#).

MIDAS Heritage – CARARE metadata mapping tables

MIDAS Theme	MIDAS Information group	MIDAS Unit name	CARARE Theme	CARARE Element name
All		Primary Reference Number	Record information	ID
		Primary Reference Number Type		Not mapped
Heritage Asset	Area, Monument, Artefact, Ecofact	Heritage Asset Name	Heritage Asset	Appellation/name
		Compiler (Organisation)	Record information	
		Compiler (Person)		Creation/Actor
		Date of Compilation		
		Date of Last Update		Update/Date
		Entry Type		Type
		External Information System		relations/Appellation
		External Information System Primary Reference Number	Heritage Asset	relations/targetOfRelation
		Description	Heritage Asset	Description/full Description/summary
		Description Type		
		Protection Type	Heritage Asset	Designations/protection type
			Heritage Asset	Designations/grade
			Heritage Asset	Designations/date from
	Heritage Asset	Designations/date to		
Right Note		Record	Rights	

		information	
	Right Type		
		Heritage Asset	Relations
Area	Area Type	Heritage Asset	Characters/ heritage asset type
	Evidence		
Monument	Monument Type	Heritage Asset	Characters/ heritage asset type
	Currency		
	Evidence		
	Material	Heritage Asset	Characters/materials
	Material Component		
	Material Component Note		
	Material Name		
	Component		
	Prime Motive Power	Heritage asset	Craft/propulsion
	Craft type	Heritage asset	Characters/ heritage asset type
	Departure (Place)	Heritage asset	Craft/lastjourneydetails/Departure
	Destination	Heritage asset	Craft/lastjourneydetails/Destination
	Manner of Loss	Heritage asset	Craft/lastjourneydetails/Mannerofloss
	Nationality	Heritage asset	Craft/nationality
	Registration Place	Heritage asset	Craft/place of registration
	Associated Goods	Heritage asset	Craft/lastjourneydetails/Cargo
	Construction Method	Heritage asset	Craft/construction method
	Dimension	Heritage asset	Dimensions/measurement type
	Dimension Measurement Unit	Heritage asset	Dimensions/unit
	Dimension Value	Heritage asset	Dimensions/value
		Heritage asset	Dimensions/scale
Condition	Heritage asset	Conditions/Condition	
		Heritage asset	Conditions/Condition assessment

		Condition Date	Heritage asset	Conditions/Condition date
			Heritage asset	Conditions/Relations
		Inscription	Heritage asset	Inscriptions
		Inscription Note	Heritage asset	Inscriptions
	Artefact/ Ecofact	Artefact/Ecofact Type	Heritage asset	Characters/Heritage asset type
		Condition	Heritage asset	Conditions/condition
			Heritage asset	Conditions/Condition assessment
		Condition Date	Heritage asset	Conditions/condition date
			Heritage asset	Conditions/Relations
		Recovery Method	Activity	eventType
		Artefact Name Type	Heritage asset	Characters/Heritage asset type
			Activity	description
		Recovery Purpose		
		Production Method	Heritage asset	description
		Production Technique	Heritage asset	description
		Dimension	Heritage asset	Dimensions/measurement type
		Dimension Measurement Unit	Heritage asset	Dimensions/unit
		Dimension Value	Heritage asset	Dimensions/value
			Heritage asset	Dimensions/scale
		Evidence	Heritage asset	description
		Completeness	Heritage asset	Conditions/Condition assessment
		Conservation Treatment Priority	Heritage asset	Conditions/Condition assessment
		Environmental Condition Note	Heritage asset	Conditions/Condition assessment
		Inscription Content	Heritage asset	Inscriptions
		Inscription Note	Heritage asset	description
		Material	Heritage Asset	Characters/materials

		Material Component	Heritage Asset	Characters/materials
		Material Component Note	Heritage asset	description
		Material Name	Heritage Asset	Characters/materials
		Component	Heritage asset	description
		Collection Extent		
		Storage Location	Heritage asset	Repository location
Activity	Activity (All)	Activity Name	Activity	Appellation/name
		Description	Activity	Description
		Description Type		
		Compiler (Organisation)	Record information	
		Compiler (Person)		Creation/Actor
		Date of Compilation		Creation/Date
		Date of Last Update		Update/Date
		External Information System	Activity	relations/Appellation
	External Information System Primary Reference Number	Activity	relations/targetOfRelation	
			Activity	Relations
	Investigative Activity;	Activity Objective		
		Activity Type	Activity	Activity/Event type
		Work Status		
	Designation and Protection	Statutory Name		
		Statutory Description		
		Entry Type		
Protection Type				
Protection Grade				

		Protection Start Date		
		Protection End Date		
	Heritage Asset Management Activity	Entry type	Activity	Activity/Event type
		Management Activity Method	Activity	Activity/Event method
		Management Activity Type	Activity	Activity/Event type
			Activity	Activity/Materials and techniques used
		Work Status		
			Activity	Activity/Assessments
	Casework and Consultation	Management Proposal Type	Activity	Activity/Event type
		Notification Date	Activity	Temporal/timespan/startDate
		Management Proposal Work Proposed	Activity	Description
		Management Proposal Recommendation	Activity	Description
		Case Status		
		Management Proposal Outcome	Activity	Description
Authorisation Required				
Research and Analysis	Entry Type	Activity	Activity/Event type	
	Activity Type	Activity	Activity/Event type	
	Activity Objective	Activity	Description	
	Work Status	Activity	Description	
	Recovery Method	Activity	Activity/Event method	
	Potential (Key Item Flag)			

		Potential (Note)	Activity	Description	
	Historical Event	Historical Event Type	Activity	Activity/Event type	
Information Source	Information Source (All)	Information Source Title	Heritage asset Digital resource	References/Appellation/name Appellation/name	
		Description	Digital resource	Description	
		Description Type			
			Digital resource	Note	
		Compiler (Organisation)	Record information		
		Compiler (Person)			Creation/Actor
		Date of Compilation			Creation/Date
		Date of Last Update			Update/Date
		Entry Type		Type	
		External Information System			
External Information System Primary Reference Number					
Archive and Bibliography		Statement of Responsibility	Heritage asset Digital Resource	References/Actors Actors	
		Archive/ Source Type	Heritage asset Digital resource	References/Type Type	
		Archive/ Source Location	Heritage asset	References/Note	
		Archive/ Source Reference	Heritage asset	References/Relations	
		Archive Extent	Heritage asset	References/Extent	
		Archive/	Heritage asset	References/Medium	

		Source Format	Digital Resource Digital Resource	Format Medium
		Subject	Heritage asset Digital resource	References/Subject Subject
			Digital resource	Spatial
			Digital resource	Temporal
		Date of Origination	Digital resource	Created
		Language	Heritage asset Digital resource	References/Note Language
		Right Note	Heritage asset Digital resource	References/Rights Provenance
		Right Type	Heritage asset	References/Rights
			Heritage asset Digital resource	References/Publication statement/publisher References/Publication statement/place of publication References/Publication statement/date of publication Publication statement/publisher Publication statement/place of publication Publication statement/date of publication
			Digital resource	Link
			Digital resource	IsShownAt
			Digital resource	Resource Metadata Location
		Narrative and Synthesis	Statement of Responsibility	
Audience				
Educational Level				
Narrative Text				
Subject				
	Language			

		Right Note		
		Right Type		
	Management Activity Documentation	Conservation Plan		
		Maintenance Plan		
		Occupancy		
		Condition		
		Condition Statement		
		Condition Date		
		Vulnerability Level		
		Agent of Damage		
		Statement of Significance		
		Value Statement		
		Value Type		
		Characterisation statement		
Spatial Information	Location	Description		
		Description Type		
		Administrative Area Name	Heritage Asset, Activity, Digital Resource, Actors	Spatial/Location set/address/admin area Spatial/Location set/address/country
		Administrative Area Type		
		Currency		
		Locality	Heritage Asset, Activity, Digital Resource, Actors	Spatial/Location set/address/locality
		Named Location	Heritage Asset, Activity, Digital Resource, Actors	Spatial/Location set/named location Spatial/Location set/historical name

		Map Sheet		
		Road or Street Name	Heritage Asset,	Spatial/Location set/address/roadname
		Number in Road or Street	Activity, Digital Resource, actors	Spatial/Location set/address/number in road
		Post Code		Spatial/Location set/address/post or zip code
		Language		
		Geopolitical Area Type	Heritage Asset, Activity, Digital Resource	Spatial/Location set/geopolitical area type
		Geopolitical Area Name		Spatial/Location set/geopolitical area
		Cadastral Reference Value		Spatial/Location set/cadastral reference
		Cadastral Reference Source		
		Directions		
		Grid Reference		
		Buffer Zone Width		
		Map Depiction		Compiler (Organisation)
Compiler (Person)				
Date of Compilation				
Date of Last Update				
External Information System				
External Information System Primary Reference Number				
Data Capture Process				
Positional Accuracy				
Quality				
Spatial Feature Type	Heritage Asset,			Spatial/cartographic reference/spatial feature type

		X Coordinate	Activity, Digital Resource	Spatial/cartographic reference/coordinates/X
		Y Coordinate	Resource	Spatial/cartographic reference/coordinates/Y
				Spatial/cartographic reference/coordinates/Z
		Precision		
		Buffer Zone Width		
		Representation Source		Spatial/representations
			Heritage Asset, Activity, Digital Resource	Spatial/geometry/bounding box/min X
				Spatial/geometry/bounding box/min Y
				Spatial/geometry/bounding box/max X
				Spatial/geometry/bounding box/max Y
				Spatial/geometry/quickpoint/X
				Spatial/geometry/quickpoint/Y
		Data Capture Scale		
Temporal Information	Date and Period	Description	Heritage Asset	Temporal
		Entry Type	Digital Resource	
		Start Date	And Activity	Temporal/time span/start date
		End Date		Temporal/time span/end date
		Period (Name)		Temporal/period name
		Dimension Measurement Unit		Temporal/time span/dimension/measurement unit
		Dimension Value		Temporal/time span/dimension/value
				Temporal/time span/dimension/type
		Display Date		Temporal/Display date
		Date Range Qualifier		Temporal/time span/date range qualifier
		Scientific Date		Temporal/Scientific date
		Scientific Date Method		Temporal/Scientific date method
Actor	Actors and	Description		Actors/biographical note

Information	Role		Actors/vital dates/ Actors/place of birth Actors/place of death Actors/place of activity
	Description Type		
	Compiler (Organisation)		
	Compiler (Person)		
	Date of Compilation		
	Date of Last Update		
	External Information System		
	External Information System Primary Reference Number		
	Contact Point		Actors/Contacts/name Actors/Contacts/address Actors/Contacts/phone Actors/Contacts/fax Actors/Contacts/email
	Contact Point Type		Actors/Contacts/role
	People Name		Actors/Name
	Organisation Name		Actors/Name
	Person Name		Actors/Name
	Occupation		
Role		Actors/Roles	

MIDAS XML to CARARE mapping

Event

MIDAS XML			CARARE	
Event.xsd	Events/ meta	/title	collection informatio n/	title
		/subject		keywords
		/keywords		contacts/name
		/contacts/contact/name/title		contacts/name
		/contacts/contact/name/firstname		contacts/name
		/contacts/contact/name/lastname		contacts/name
		/contacts/contact/name/othername		contacts/name
		/contacts/contact/organisation		contacts/organization
		/contacts/contact/role		contacts/role
		/contact/address/streetaddress		contacts/address/buildingName
				contacts/address/numberInRoad
				contacts/address/roadname
		/contact/address/city		contacts/address/townOrCity
				contacts/address/locality
		/contact/address/adminarea		contacts/address/adminArea
		/contact/address/postcode		contacts/address/postcodeOrZipcode
		/contact/address/country		contacts/address/country
		/contact/phone		contacts/phone
		/contact/fax		contacts/fax
		/contact/email		contacts/email
/rights/copyright/holder	rights/copyright/rightsHolder			
/rights/copyright/year	rights/copyright/rightsDates			
/rights/copyright/statement	rights/copyright/creditLine			
/rights/accessrights/grantedto	rights/accessRights/grantedTo			
/rights/accessrights/conditions	rights/accessRights/conditions			
/rights/accessrights/datefrom	rights/accessRights/dateFrom			
/rights/accessrights/dateto	rights/accessRights/dateTo			
/rights/accessrights/statement	rights/accessRights/statement			

	/rights/reproductionrights/statement	rights/reproductionRights/statement
	/rights/reproductionrights/statement/contact/name/title	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/name
	/rights/reproductionrights/statement/contact/name/firstname	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/name
	/rights/reproductionrights/statement/contact/name/lastname	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/name
	/rights/reproductionrights/statement/contact/name/othername	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/name
	/rights/reproductionrights/statement/contact/organisation	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/organization
	/rights/reproductionrights/statement/contact/role	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/role
	/rights/reproductionrights/statement/contact/address/streetaddress	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/buildingName
		rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/numberInRoad
		rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/roadname
		rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/townOrCity
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	/Characters/character/type/annex/artefact /Temporal/span/start/appellation		characters/temporal/timeSpan/dimension
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		/relationships/related/has_casework	relations/typeOfRelation relations/targetOfRelation relations/Appellation/name relations/Appellation/id

References

The MIDAS References theme maps to CARARE Digital Resources IF

the reference is to a digital object being made accessible to Europeana by the owner of the inventory ELSE

MIDAS references map to CARARE HeritageAssetIdentification/references (references to analogue and digital resources which are not being made accessible to Europeana by the owner of the inventory).

MIDAS XML		CARARE	
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			contacts/address/roadname
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	/discovery/circumstance		description
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	/related		characters/dimensions/value
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			relations/targetOfRelation
			relations/Appellation/name
			relations/Appellation/id
	/Objectannex/craft/crafttype		characters/HeritageAssetType/
	/Objectannex/craft /placeofregistration		characters/craft/placeOfRegistration

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		characters/dimensions/units
	/Objectannex/craft /dimension	characters/dimensions/scale
		characters/dimensions/value
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	/Objectannex artefact/materialtype	characters/materials
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	/Objectannex artefact/description/summary	description
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		characters/temporal/timeSpan/endDate
		characters/temporal/scientificDate
		characters/temporal/scientificDateMethod
		repositoryLocation

Casework

MIDAS XML		CARARE	
Casework.xsd	Casework/ meta	/title	Collection
		/subject	information/
		/keywords	title
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		/contacts/contact/name/lastname	
		/contacts/contact/name/othername	
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		/contact/address/city	contacts/address/roadname
			contacts/address/townOrCity
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		/contact/address/postcode	contacts/address/adminArea
		/contact/address/country	contacts/address/postcodeOrZipcode
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		/contact/email	contacts/fax
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		/rights/accessrights/statement	rights/accessRights/dateTo
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		rights/licence
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		statement
		language
	/creation/createdon	creation/createdOn

	/creation/query	creation/query
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		/coverage/Temporal/span/end		coverage/temporal/timeSpan/endDate
				coverage/temporal/timeSpan/dateRangeQualifier
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		recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/role		
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			recordInformation/rights
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		actors/placeOfDeath
		actors/placeOfActivity
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	/description/summary	Description
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	/Characters/character/workproposed	EventType
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	/decision/recommendation	
	/decision/dateofrecommendation	temporal/timeSpan/endDate
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	/decision/finaloutcome	Description
	/note	Description
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D2.2.3 3.2

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LIDO – CARARE metadata mapping

Revision: [final]

Authors:

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02	31/1/11	D. Trivela	NTUA	Integrating comments from Rimvydas Laužikas, Emilia Masci

Statement of originality:

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

3.2 LIDO – CARARE metadata mapping

Lightweight Information Describing Objects (LIDO) was developed by CIDOC Working Group Harvesting and Integration with the purpose of contributing content to cultural heritage repositories. LIDO satisfies the need for a convenient common instrument for providing core data from different collections, data structures or software systems. The necessity for a common schema emerged as it was both time consuming and costly to integrate information from different resources in the same portal, considering that each resource has potentially a different metadata format. LIDO was developed to overcome this situation. It was implemented by the collective efforts and support from: the CDWA Lite Advisory Committee, the Documentation Committee of the German Museums Association, the CDWA Lite – museumdat WorkingGroup, the CIDOC CRM Special Interest Group and the Athena Project.

LIDO is an XML harvesting schema intended for delivering metadata, for use in a variety of online services, from an organization's on line collections database to portals of aggregated resources, as well as exposing, sharing and connecting data on the web (<http://www.lido-schema.org/schema/v0.9/lido-v0.9-specification.pdf>). It is capable of supporting the full range of descriptive information about museum objects. Particularly, it supports all kinds of objects, such as art, cultural, technology and natural science and can be used by multilingual portals. It is not intended to be used for proper cataloguing or to support loan and acquisition activities.

The architecture of LIDO is based on a nested set of “wrapper” and “set” elements which structure records in culturally significant ways. The development of its design was inspired by CIDOC CRM resulting into a consistent event-centric schema. Event-centric approaches consider that descriptions of objects should focus on describing the various events in which objects have participated. For instance, the creation, collection and use of an object are defined as events that are related to entities such as dates, places and actors.

The strength of LIDO lies not only on its ability to support extensive range of information, but also on its flexibility. LIDO defines seven groups of information of which only four are mandatory allowing for as large a variety of completeness of information as possible. This enables the organizations to choose which data they wish to provide to a portal and publish online. The mandatory fields are related to the definition of the type of the object described, its title and its record.

The structural elements of LIDO contain “data elements” which hold the information that is being harvested and is delivered to the user of the service environment. It allows an organization to support not only optimized searching and retrieval processes, but also the online presentation of the information and the demonstration of the sources of the data to the user of the portal. To succeed this, it allows the organization to provide indexing and display information and at the same time, supports the recording of information related to the sources of the data within a controlled terminology.

Construction Principles

The construction principles of LIDO (<http://www.athenaeurope.org/getFile.php?id=559>) are the following:

- To provide a specification and related XML schema that describes cultural materials in a meaningful and comprehensive manner
- To allow the contribution of data and images related to described objects to union catalogues
- A record should provide all the necessary information for display and retrieval of a described object
- Individual data providers should be able to define the level of richness of the contributed metadata records
- Links from contributed metadata back to records in their “home” context should be provided
- It should supply optimized metadata for retrieval and display, with clear distinction between display and indexing elements
- To provide references to controlled environment

Conceptually the information in a LIDO record is organized in seven areas, of which four have descriptive and three administrative character. The descriptive metadata of an object record hold information about its type, identification, the events that has participated in and the relations to other resources. The administrative metadata hold information about the rights, the record and any digital resource being supplied to the service environment.

Crosswalks between LIDO and CARARE

For the sake of completion this document includes tables for both ‘LIDO to CARARE’ and ‘CARARE to LIDO’ crosswalks.

CROSSWALK TABLE BETWEEN LIDO AND CARARE

LIDO ELEMENTS		CARARE ELEMENTS
Global Wrapper elements		
lidoWrap/	Lido	
	lidoRecID	
	objectPublishedID	
	category/conceptID	
	category/term	
	descriptiveMetadata/objectClassificationWrap/	
	descriptiveMetadata/objectIdentification/	
	descriptiveMetadata/eventWrap/	
	descriptiveMetadata/objectRelationWrap/	
	administrativeMetadata/rightsWorkWrap/	
	administrativeMetadata/recordWrap/	
	administrativeMetadata/resourceWrap/	
lido/	lidoRecID	
	objectPublishedID	
	category/conceptID	
	category/term	
	descriptiveMetadata/objectClassificationWrap/	
	descriptiveMetadata/objectIdentificationWrap/	
	descriptiveMetadata/eventWrap/	

	descriptiveMetadata/objectRelationWrap/	
	administrativeMetadata/rightsWorkWrap/	
	administrativeMetadata/recordWrap/	
	administrativeMetadata/resourceWrap/	
descriptiveMetadata/	objectClassificationWrap/	
	objectIdentificationWrap/	
	eventWrap/	
	objectRelationWrap/	
administrativeMetadata/	rightsWorkWrap/	
	recordWrap/	
	resourceWrap/	
Object Classification Elements		
objectClassificationWrap/	objectWorkTypeWrap/	
	classificationWrap/	
objectWorkTypeWrap/	objectWorkType/conceptID	
	objectWorkType/term	
classificationWrap/	classification/conceptID	
	classification/term	heritageAssetIdentification/characters/HeritageAssetType/
Object Identification elements		
objectIdentificationWrap/ titleWrap/	titleSet	heritageAssetIdentification/appellation/name
	appellationValue	
	sourceAppellation	
objectIdentificationWrap/inscriptionsWrap/	Inscriptions	heritageAssetIdentification/characters/inscriptions

	inscriptionTranscription	
	inscriptionDescription /descriptiveNoteID	
	inscriptionDescription /descriptiveNote Value	heritageAssetIdentification/characters/inscriptions
	inscriptionDescription /sourceDescriptiveNote	
objectIdentificationWrap/repositoryWrap/	repositorySet /repositoryName/legalBodyID	
	repositorySet /repositoryName/legalBodyName/ appellationValue	
	repositorySet /repositoryName/legalBodyName/ sourceAppellation	
	repositorySet /repositoryName/legalBodyWebLink	
	repositorySet /workID	heritageAssetIdentification/appellation/id
	repositorySet /repositoryLocation/placeID	
	repositorySet /repositoryLocation/namePlaceSet/ appellationValue	heritageAssetIdentification/characters/repositoryLocation
	repositorySet /repositoryLocation/namePlaceSet/ sourceAppellation	
	repositorySet /repositoryLocation/gml	heritageAssetIdentification/

		spatial/locationSet/ GeopoliticalArea heritageAssetIdentification/ spatial/geometry/quickpoint/x heritageAssetIdentification/ spatial/geometry/quickpoint/y
	repositorySet /repositoryLocation/partOfPlace/place ID	
	repositorySet /repositoryLocation/partOfPlace/ namePlaceSet/appellationValue	heritageAssetIdentification/ spatial/locationSet/historicalname heritageAssetIdentification/ spatial/locationSet/namedLocation
	repositorySet /repositoryLocation/partOfPlace/ namePlaceSet/sourceAppellation	
	repositorySet /repositoryLocation/partOfPlace/gml	heritageAssetIdentification/ spatial/geometry/quickpoint/x heritageAssetIdentification/ spatial/geometry/quickpoint/y heritageAssetIdentification/ spatial/geometry/quickpoint/z
	repositorySet /repositoryLocation/partOfPlace/partO fPlace	

	repositorySet /repositoryLocation/partOfPlace/place Classification/conceptID	
	repositorySet /repositoryLocation/partOfPlace/place Classification/term	
objectIdentificationWrap/displayStateEd itionWrap/	displayState	heritageAssetIdentification/ conditions/condition heritageAssetIdentification/ conditions/conditionAssessment heritageAssetIdentification/ conditions/conditionDate
	displayEdition	
	sourceStateEdition	
objectIdentificationWrap/objectDescript ionWrap/	objectDescriptionSet/ descriptiveNoteID	
	objectDescriptionSet/ descriptpiveNoteValue	heritageAssetIdentification/description heritageAssetIdentification/ characters/temporal/timeSpan/startDate heritageAssetIdentification/ characters/temporal/timeSpan/endDate
	objectDescriptionSet/	

	sourceDescriptiveNote	
objectIdentificationWrap/objectMeasurementsWrap/	objectMeasurementsSet/displayObjectMeasurements	heritageAssetIdentification/characters/dimensions
	objectMeasurementsSet/objectMeasurements/measurementsSet/measurementType	heritageAssetIdentification/characters/dimensions/measurementType
	objectMeasurementsSet/objectMeasurements/measurementsSet/measurementUnit	heritageAssetIdentification/characters/dimensions/units
	objectMeasurementsSet/objectMeasurements/measurementsSet/measurementValue	heritageAssetIdentification/characters/dimensions/value
	objectMeasurementsSet/objectMeasurements/exentMeasurements	
	objectMeasurementsSet/objectMeasurements/qualifierMeasurements	
	objectMeasurementsSet/objectMeasurements/formatMeasurements	
	objectMeasurementsSet/objectMeasurements/shapeMeasurements	
	objectMeasurementsSet/objectMeasurements/scaleMeasurements	heritageAssetIdentification/characters/dimensions/scale
Event elements		
eventWrap/	eventSet/displayEvent	
	eventSet/event/eventType	
	eventSet/event/eventType/conceptID	

	eventSet/event/eventType/term	activity/ EventType
	eventSet/event/roleInEvent/conceptID	
	eventSet/event/roleInEvent/term	activity/ appellation/name
	eventSet/event/eventName/appellationValue	activity/ appellation/name
	eventSet/event/eventName/sourceAppellation	
	eventSet/event/eventActor/ displayActorInRole	heritageAssetIdentification/ actors/name heritageAssetIdentification/ actors/roles
	eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/actorID	heritageAssetIdentification/ actors/id activity/actors/id
	eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/name ActorSet/appellationValue	heritageAssetIdentification/ actors/name activity/actors/name
	eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/name ActorSet/sourceAppellation	
	eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/nationalityActor/conceptID	
	eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/nationality	activity/

	alityActor/term	actors/placeOfBirth
	eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/vitalDatesActor/earliestDate	heritageAssetIdentification/actors/vitalDates activity/actors/vitalDates/birthDate
	eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/vitalDatesActor/latestDate	heritageAssetIdentification/actors/vitalDates activity/actors/vitalDates/deathDate
	eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/actorID/genderActor	heritageAssetIdentification/actors/actorType
	eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/roleActor/conceptID	
	eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/roleActor/term	heritageAssetIdentification/actors/contacts/role
	eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/attributionQualifierActor	
	eventSet/event/eventActoractorInRole/actor/extentActor	
	eventSet/event/culture/conceptID	
	eventSet/event/culture/term	
	eventSet/event/eventDate/displayDate	heritageAssetIdentification/conditions/conditionDate

		heritageAssetIdentification/ characters/temporal/displayDate
		activity/ temporal/displayDate
	eventSet/event/eventDate/Date/earliestDate	activity/temporal/timeSpan/startDate
	eventSet/event/Date/latestDate	activity/ temporal/timeSpan/endDate
	eventSet/event/periodName/conceptID	
	eventSet/event/periodName/Term	activity/ temporal/periodName
	eventSet/event/eventPlace/displayPlace	heritageAssetIdentification/ recordInformation/creation/actor/placeOfActivity
		heritageAssetIdentification/ characters/craft/placeOfRegistration
		heritageAssetIdentification/ characters/craft/nationality
	eventSet/event/eventPlace/place/placeID	
	eventSet/event/eventPlace/place/ namePlaceSet/appellationValue	activity/spatial/locationSet/namedLocation
	eventSet/event/eventPlace/place/namePlaceSet/ sourceAppellation	

	eventSet/event/eventPlace/place/gml	
	eventSet/event/eventPlace/partOfPlace/ placeID	
	eventSet/event/eventPlace/partOfPlace/namePlaceS et/appellationValue	
	eventSet/event/eventPlace/partOfPlace/namePlaceS et/sourceAppellation	
	eventSet/event/eventPlace/partOfPlace/gml	
	eventSet/event/eventPlace/partOfPlace/partOfPlace	
	eventSet/event/eventPlace/partOfPlace/placeClassif ication/conceptID	
	eventSet/event/eventPlace/partOfPlace/placeClassif ication/term	
	eventSet/event/eventPlace/placeClassification/conc eptID	
	eventSet/event/eventPlace/placeClassification/term	
	eventSet/event/eventMethod/conceptID	
	eventSet/event/eventMethod/term	heritageAssetIdentification/ characters/craft/constructionMethod
	eventSet/event/eventMaterialsTech/displayMaterial sTech	
	eventSet/event/eventMaterialsTech/materialsTech/t ermMaterialsTech/conceptID	
	eventSet/event/eventMaterialsTech/materialsTech/t ermMaterialsTech/term	heritageAssetIdentification/ characters/materials
	eventSet/event/eventMaterialsTech/materialsTech/e	

	xtentMaterialsTech	
	eventSet/event/eventMaterialsTech/materialsTech/s ourceMaterialsTech	
	eventSet/event/thingPresent/displayObject	
	eventSet/event/thingPresent/object/objectWebReso urce	
	eventSet/event/thingPresent/object/objectID	
	eventSet/event/thingPresent/object/ objectNote	
	eventSet/event/relatedEventSet/relatedEvent/displa yEvent	
	eventSet/event/relatedEventSet/relatedEvent/event	
	eventSet/event/relatedEventSet/relatedEvent RelType/conceptID	
	eventSet/event/relatedEventSet/relatedEvent RelType/term	
	eventSet/event/eventDescriptionSet/ descriptiveNoteID	
	eventSet/event/eventDescriptionSet/ descriptiveNoteValue	
	eventSet/event/eventDescriptionSet/ descriptiveNoteValue	activity/description/
	eventSet/event/eventDescriptionSet/ sourceDescriptiveNote	
Object Relation Elements		
objectRelationWrap/	subjectWrap/subjectSet/displaySubject	

	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/extentSubject	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/ subjectConcept/conceptID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/ subjectConcept/term	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectActor/displayActor	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectActor/actor/ actorID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectActor/actor/ nameActorSet/appellationValue	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectActor/actor/ nameActorSet/sourceAppellation	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectActor/actor/ nationalityActor/conceptID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectActor/actor/ nationalityActor/term	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectActor/actor/ vitalDatesActor/earliestDate	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectActor/actor/ vitalDatesActor/latestDate	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectActor/actor/ genderActor	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectDate/ displayDate	heritageAssetIdentification/ characters/temporal/ periodname

		heritageAssetIdentification/ characters/temporal/displayDate
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectDate/ date/earliestDate	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectDate/ latestDate	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/displa yEvent	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event/ eventID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event Type/conceptID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event Type/term	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/roleIn Event/conceptID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/roleIn Event/term	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event Name/appellationValue	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event Name/sourceAppellation	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event Actor/displayActorInRole	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event Actor/actorInRole/actor/actorID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event	

	Actor/actorInRole/actor/nameActorSet	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event Actor/actorInRole/actor/nameActorSet /appellationValue	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event Actor/actorInRole/actor/nameActorSet/ sourceAppellation	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event Actor/actorInRole/actor/ nationalityActor/conceptID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event Actor/actorInRole/actor/nationalityActor/term	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event Actor/actorInRole/actor/vitalDatesActor/earliestDate	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event Actor/actorInRole/actor/vitalDatesActor/latestDate	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event Actor/actorInRole/actor/genderActor	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event Actor/actorInRole/roleActor/conceptID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event Actor/actorInRole/roleActor/term	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event Actor/actorInRole/attributionQualifier Actor	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event	

	Actor/actorInRole/extentActor	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/culture/conceptID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/culture/term	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/eventDate/displayDate	heritageAssetIdentification/ characters/temporal/ periodname heritageAssetIdentification/ characters/temporal/displayDate
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/eventDate/date/earliestDate	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/eventDate/date/latestDate	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/periodName/conceptID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/periodName/term	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/eventPlace/displayPlace	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/eventPlace/place/placeID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/eventPlace/namePlaceSet/appellationValue	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/eventPlace/namePlaceSet/sourceAppellation	

	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/ eventPlace/gml	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/ eventPlace/partOfPlace/placeID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event Actor/eventPlace/partOfPlace/namePlaceSet/appell ationValue	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/ eventPlace/partOfPlace/namePlaceSet/sourceAppel lation	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/ eventPlace/partOfPlace/gml	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/ eventPlace/partOfPlace/partOfPlace	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/ eventPlace/partOfPlace/placeClassification/concept ID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/ eventPlace/partOfPlace/placeClassification/term	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event Method/conceptID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event Method/term	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event MaterialsTech/displayMaterialsTech	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event MaterialsTech/materialsTech/termMaterialsTech/co	

	conceptID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/eventMaterialsTech/materialsTech/termMaterialsTech/term	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/eventMaterialsTech/materialsTech/extentMaterialsTech	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/eventMaterialsTech/materialsTech/sourceMaterialsTech	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/thingPresent/displayObject	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/thingPresent/object/objectWebResource	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/thingPresent/object/objectID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/thingPresent/object/objectNote	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/relatedEventSet/relatedEvent/displayEvent	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/relatedEventSet/relatedEvent/event	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/relatedEventSet/relatedEventRelType/conceptID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/relatedEventSet/relatedEventRelType/term	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/eventDescriptionSet/descriptiveNoteID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event	

	DescriptionSet/descriptiveNote Value	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectEvent/event DescriptionSet/sourceDescriptiveNote	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectPlace/displayPlace	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectPlace/place/ placeID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectPlace/place/ namePlaceSet/appellation Value	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectPlace/place/ namePlaceSet/sourceAppellation	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectPlace/place/ gml	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectPlace/place/ partOfPlace/placeID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectPlace/place/ partOfPlace/namePlaceSet/appellation Value	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectPlace/place/ partOfPlace/namePlaceSet/ sourceAppellation	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectPlace/place/ partOfPlace/gml	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectPlace/place/ partOfPlace/partOfPlace	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectPlace/place/ partOfPlace/placeClassification/conceptID	

	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectPlace/place/partOfPlace/placeClassification/term	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectPlace/place/placeClassification/conceptID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectPlace/place/placeClassification/term	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectObject/displayObject	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectObject/object/objectWebResource	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectObject/object/objectID	
	subjectWrap/subjectSet/subject/subjectObject/object/objectNote	
	relatedWorksWrap/relatedWorkSet/relatedWork/displayObject	
	relatedWorksWrap/relatedWorkSet/relatedWork/object/objectWebResource	
	relatedWorksWrap/relatedWorkSet/relatedWork/object/objectID	
	relatedWorksWrap/relatedWorkSet/relatedWork/object/objectNote	
	relatedWorksWrap/relatedWorkSet/relatedWorkRelType/conceptID	
	relatedWorksWrap/relatedWorkSet/relatedWorkRelType/term	
Rights for Work elements		

rightsWorkWrap/	rightsWorkSet/rightsType/conceptID	
	rightsWorkSet/rightsType/term	heritageAssetIdentification/ designations/protectionType
	rightsWorkSet/rightsDate/earliestDate	heritageAssetIdentification/ designations/dateFrom
	rightsWorkSet/rightsDate/latestDate	heritageAssetIdentification/ designations/dateTo
	rightsWorkSet/rightsHolder/legalBodyID	
	rightsWorkSet/rightsHolder/legalBodyName/appellationValue	
	rightsWorkSet/rightsHolder/legalBodyName/sourceAppellation	
	rightsWorkSet/rightsHolder/legalBodyWebLink	
	rightsWorkSet/creditLine	
Record elements		
recordWrap/	recordID	heritageAssetIdentification/ recordInformation/id
	recordType/contentID	
	recordType/term	heritageAssetIdentification/ recordInformation/type
	recordSource/legalBodyID	heritageAssetIdentification/ recordInformation/creation/actor/id
	recordSource/legalBodyName/appellationValue	heritageAssetIdentification/ recordInformation/creation/actor/name

		heritageAssetIdentification/ recordInformation/update/actor/name
	recordSource/legalBodyName/sourceAppellation	
	recordSource/legalBodyWeblink	
	recordRights/rightsType/conceptID	
	recordRights/rightsType/term	
	recordRights/rightsDate/earliestDate	heritageAssetIdentification/ recordInformation/rights/copyright/rightsDates
		heritageAssetIdentification/ recordInformation/rights/accessRights/dateFrom
	recordRights/rightsDate/latestDate	heritageAssetIdentification/ recordInformation/rights/copyright/rightsDates
		heritageAssetIdentification/ recordInformation/rights/accessRights/dateTo
	recordRights/rightsHolder/legalBodyID	
	recordRights/rightsHolder/legalBodyName/appellationValue	heritageAssetIdentification/ recordInformation/rights/copyright/rightsHolder
	recordRights/rightsHolder/legalBodyName/sourceAppellation	
	recordRights/rightsHolder/legalBodyWeblink	
	recordRights/creditLine	heritageAssetIdentification/ recordInformation/rights/copyright/creditLine

		heritageAssetIdentification/ recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/statement
	recordInfoSet/recordInfoID	heritageAssetIdentification/ recordInformation/id digitalResource/ recordInformation/id
	recordInfoSet/recordInfoLink	
	recordInfoSet/recordMetadataDate	heritageAssetIdentification/ recordInformation/update/ date
Resource Elements		
resourceWrap/	resourceSet/resourceID	heritageAssetIdentification/ references/appellation/id digitalResource/ appellation/id
	resourceSet/resourceRepresentation/ linkResource	heritageAssetIdentification/ references/appellation/name digitalResource/ appellation/name digitalResource/ Link
	resourceSet/resourceRepresentation/resourceMeasurementsSet/measurementType	
	resourceSet/resourceRepresentation/resourceMeasurementsSet/measurementType	

	rementsSet/measurementUnit	
	resourceSet/resourceRepresentation/resourceMeasurementsSet/measurementValue	
	resourceSet/resourceType/conceptID	
	resourceSet/resourceType/term	heritageAssetIdentification/ references/medium digitalResource/ Medium digitalResource/ Type
	resourceSet/resourceRelType/conceptID	
	resourceSet/resourceRelType/term	heritageAssetIdentification/ references/appellation heritageAssetIdentification/ references/type digitalResource / references/appellation digitalResource / references/type
	resourceSet/resourcePerspective/conceptID	
	resourceSet/resourcePerspective/term	digitalResource/format
	resourceSet/resourceDescription	digitalResource/ Description

	resourceSet/displayDate	digitalResource/ temporal/periodName digitalResource/ temporal/displayDate digitalResource/ publicationstatement/date
	resourceSet/date/earliestDate	digitalResource/ temporal/timeSpan/ startDate
	resourceSet/date/latestDate	digitalResource/ temporal/timeSpan/endDate
	resourceSet/resourceSource/legalBodyID	heritageAssetIdentification/ references/actors/ID digitalResource/ actors/ID
	resourceSet/resourceSource/legalBodyName/appellationValue	heritageAssetIdentification/ references/actors/name digitalResource/ actors/name
	resourceSet/resourceSource/legalBodyName/sourceAppellation	
	resourceSet/resourceSource/legalBodyWeblink	

	resourceSet/rightsResource/rightsType/conceptID	
	resourceSet/rightsResource/rightsType/term	heritageAssetIdentification/Rights/License Digital resource/Rights/License
	resourceSet/rightsResource/rightsDate/ earliestDate	heritageAssetIdentification/ references/rights/copyright/rightsDates heritageAssetIdentification/ references/rights/ accessRights/dateFrom digitalResource/ rights/copyright/rightsDates digitalResource/ rights/accessRights/dateFrom
	resourceSet/rightsResource/rightsDate/ latestDate	heritageAssetIdentification/ references/rights/copyright/rightsDates heritageAssetIdentification/ references/rights/ accessRights/dateTo digitalResource/ rights/copyright/rightsDates digitalResource/ rights/accessRights/dateTo

	resourceSet/rightsResource/rightsHolder/legalBody ID	
	resourceSet/rightsResource/rightsHolder/legalBody Name/appellationValue	<p>heritageAssetIdentification/ references/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/ organization</p> <p>digitalResource/ rights/copyright/rights Holder</p>
	resourceSet/rightsResource/rightsHolder/legalBody Name/sourceAppellation	
	resourceSet/rightsResource/rightsHolder/legalBody Weblink	
	resourceSet/rightsResource/creditLine	<p>heritageAssetIdentification/ references/rights/copyright/creditLine</p> <p>heritageAssetIdentification/ references/rights/access Rights/conditions</p> <p>digitalResource/ rights/copyright/creditLine</p>

		digitalResource/ rights/accessRights/ Conditions
		digitalResource/ rights/accessRights/ statement
		digitalResource/ rights/reproductionRights/ statement

CROSSWALK TABLE BETWEEN CARARE AND LIDO

CARARE		LIDO
collectionInformation/ title		
collectionInformation/ keywords		
collectionInformation/ contacts/name		
collectionInformation/ contacts/role		
collectionInformation/ contacts/organization		
collectionInformation/ contacts/address/buildingName		

collectionInformation/ rights/accessRights/dateFrom		
collectionInformation/ rights/accessRights/dateTo		
collectionInformation/ rights/accessRights/statement		
collectionInformation/ rights/reproductionRights/statement		
collectionInformation/ rights/reproductionRights/contacts/name		
collectionInformation/ rights/reproductionRights/contacts/role		
collectionInformation/ rights/reproductionRights/contacts/organization		
collectionInformation/ rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/buildingName		
collectionInformation/ rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/numberInRoad		
collectionInformation/ rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/roadname		
collectionInformation/ rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/townOrCity		
collectionInformation/ rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/postcodeOrZipcode		
collectionInformation/ rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/locality		
collectionInformation/ rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/adminArea		
collectionInformation/ rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/country		

collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/phone	
collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/fax	
collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/email	
collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/fees	
collectionInformation/	rights/licence	
collectionInformation/	Source	
collectionInformation/	language	
collectionInformation/	statement	
collectionInformation/	creation/createdOn	
collectionInformation/	creation/query	
collectionInformation/	coverage/temporal	
collectionInformation/	coverage/temporal/timeSpan/startDate	
collectionInformation/	coverage/temporal/timeSpan/endDate	
collectionInformation/	coverage/temporal/timeSpan/dimension	
collectionInformation/	coverage/temporal/timeSpan/dateRangeQualifier	

collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/locationSet/geopoliticalAreaType	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/locationSet/cadastralReference	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/locationSet/historicalname	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/locationSet/spatialReferenceSystem	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/cartographicReference/spatialFeatureType	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/cartographicReference/coordinates/x	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/cartographicReference/coordinates/y	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/cartographicReference/coordinates/Z	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/geometry/boundingBox/minx	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/geometry/boundingBox/maxX	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/geometry/boundingBox/minY	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/geometry/boundingBox/maxY	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/geometry/quickpoint/x	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/geometry/quickpoint/y	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/geometry/entity	

collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/geometry/storedPrecision	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/geometry/height	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/geometry/area	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/representations	
collectionInformation/	spatialReferenceSystem	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/id	recordWrap/ recordID recordWrap/ recordInfoSet/recordInfoID
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/type	recordWrap/ recordType/term
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/source	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/country	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/id	recordWrap/ recordSource/legalBodyID
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/name	recordWrap/ recordSource/legalBodyName/appellationValue
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/actorType	

heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/roles	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/name	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/role	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/organization	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/address/buildingName	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/address/NumberInRoad	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/address/roadname	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/address/townOrCity	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/address/postcodeOrZipcode	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/address/locality	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/adminArea	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/address/country	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/phone	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/fax	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/email	

heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/vitalDates/birthDate	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/vitalDates/deathDate	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/vitalDates/type	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/placeOfBirth	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/placeOfDeath	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/placeOfActivity	eventWrap/eventSet/event/eventPlace/displayPlace
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/actor/bibliographicNote	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/creation/date	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/id	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/name	recordWrap/ recordSource/legalBodyName/appellationValue
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/actorType	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/roles	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/name	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/role	

heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/organization	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/address/buildingName	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/address/NumberInRoad	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/address/roadname	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/address/townOrCity	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/address/postcodeOrZipcode	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/address/locality	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/adminArea	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/address/country	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/phone	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/fax	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/email	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/vitalDates/birthDate	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/deathDate	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/type	

heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/placeOfBirth	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/placeOfDeath	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/placeOfActivity	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/actor/bibliographicNote	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/update/date	recordWrap/recordInfoSet/recordMetadataDate
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/language	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/copyright/rightsHolder	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/copyright/rightsDates	recordWrap/ recordRights/rightsDate/latestDate
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/copyright/creditLine	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/accessRights/grantedTo	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/accessRights/conditions	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/accessRights/dateFrom	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/accessRights/dateTo	recordWrap/ recordRights/rightsDate/latestDate
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/accessRights/statement	

heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/statement	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/name	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/role	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/organization	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/buildingName	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/numberInRoad	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/roadname	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/townOrCity	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/postcodeOrZipcode	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/locality	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/adminArea	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/country	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/phone	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/fax	
heritageAssetIdentification/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/email	

heritageAssetIdentification/ recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/fees		
heritageAssetIdentification/ recordInformation/rights/licence		
heritageAssetIdentification/ recordInformation/keywords		
heritageAssetIdentification/ appellation/name		objectIdentificationWrap/ titleWrap/ titleSet
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heritageAssetIdentification/ description		objectIdentificationWrap/objectDescriptionWrap/ objectDescriptionSet/ descripiveNoteValue
heritageAssetIdentification/ actors/id		eventWrap/eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/actorID
heritageAssetIdentification/ actors/name		eventWrap/eventSet/event/eventActor/ displayActorInRole eventWrap/eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/nameActorSet/ap pellationValue
heritageAssetIdentification/ actors/actorType		eventWrap/eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/actorID/genderAc tor
heritageAssetIdentification/ actors/roles		eventWrap/eventSet/event/eventActor/ displayActorInRole
heritageAssetIdentification/ actors/contacts/name		

heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/contacts/role	eventWrap/eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/roleActor/term
heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/contacts/organization	
heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/contacts/address/buildingName	
heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/contacts/address/NumberInRoad	
heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/contacts/address/roadname	
heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/contacts/address/townOrCity	
heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/contacts/address/postcodeOrZipcode	
heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/contacts/address/locality	
heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/contacts/address/adminArea	
heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/contacts/address/country	
heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/contacts/phone	
heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/contacts/fax	
heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/contacts/email	
heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/vitalDates/birthDate	eventWrap/eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/vitalDatesActor/earliestDate
heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/vitalDates/deathDate	eventWrap/eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/vitalDatesActor/latestDate

heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/vitalDates/type	
heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/placeOfBirth	
heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/placeOfDeath	
heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/placeOfActivity	
heritageAssetIdentification/	actors/biographicalNote	
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heritageAssetIdentification/	designations/grade	
heritageAssetIdentification/	designations/dateFrom	rightsWorkWrap/ rightsWorkSet/rightsType/ earliestDate
heritageAssetIdentification/	designations/dateTo	rightsWorkWrap/ rightsWorkSet/rightsType/ latestDate
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heritageAssetIdentification/	conditions/conditionAssessment	objectIdentificationWrap/displayStateEditionWrap/ displayState
heritageAssetIdentification/	conditions/conditionDate	objectIdentificationWrap/displayStateEditionWrap/ displayState

		eventWrap/eventSet/event/eventDate/displayDate
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heritageAssetIdentification/	characters/temporal/timeSpan/endDate	objectIdentificationWrap/objectDescriptionWrap/ objectDescriptionSet/ descriptiveNoteValue
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heritageAssetIdentification/	characters/temporal/timeSpan/dateRangeQualifier	
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heritageAssetIdentification/	characters/temporal/scientificDateMethod	
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ntification/		IsTech/term
heritageAssetIdentification/	characters/inscriptions	objectIdentificationWrap/inscriptionsWrap/ Inscriptions objectIdentificationWrap/inscriptionsWrap/ inscriptionDescription /descriptiveNoteValue
heritageAssetIdentification/	characters/dimensions/measurementType	objectIdentificationWrap/objectMeasurementsWrap/objectMeasurementsSet/displayObject Measurements objectIdentificationWrap/objectMeasurementsWrap/objectMeasurementsSet/objectMeasurements/measurementsSet/measurementType
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heritageAssetIdentification/	characters/dimensions/scale	objectIdentificationWrap/objectMeasurementsWrap/objectMeasurementsSet/displayObject Measurements objectIdentificationWrap/objectMeasurementsWrap/objectMeasurementsSet/objectMeasurements/scaleMeasurements
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heritageAssetIdentification/	characters/craft/nationality	eventWrap/eventSet/event/eventPlace/displayPlace
heritageAssetIdentification/	characters/craft/constructionMethod	eventWrap/eventSet/event/eventMethod/term
heritageAssetIdentification/	characters/craft/propulsion	
heritageAssetIdentification/	characters/craft/lastJourneyDetails/departure	
heritageAssetIdentification/	characters/craft/lastJourneyDetails/destination	
heritageAssetIdentification/	characters/craft/lastJourneyDetails/cargo	
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heritageAssetIdentification/	characters/craft/lastJourneyDetails/dateOfLoss	
heritageAssetIdentification/	repositoryLocation	objectIdentificationWrap/repositoryWrap/repositorySet /repositoryLocation/namePlaceSet/ appellationValue
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heritageAssetIdentification/	spatial/locationSet/address/townOrCity	
heritageAssetIdentification/	spatial/locationSet/address/postcodeOrZipcode	
heritageAssetIdentification/	spatial/locationSet/address/locality	
heritageAssetIdentification/	spatial/locationSet/address/adminArea	
heritageAssetIdentification/	spatial/locationSet/address/cocountry	
heritageAssetIdentification/	spatial/locationSet/GeopoliticalArea	objectIdentificationWrap/repositoryWrap/ repositorySet /repositoryLocation/gml
heritageAssetIdentification/	spatial/locationSet/geopoliticalAreaType	
heritageAssetIdentification/	spatial/locationSet/cadastralReference	
heritageAssetIdentification/	spatial/locationSet/historicalname	objectIdentificationWrap/repositoryWrap/ repositorySet /repositoryLocation/partOfPlace/ namePlaceSet/appellationValue
heritageAssetIde	spatial/locationSet/spatialReferenceSystem	

ntification/		
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heritageAssetIdentification/	spatial/cartographicReference/coordinates/y	
heritageAssetIdentification/	spatial/cartographicReference/coordinates/Z	
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heritageAssetIdentification/	spatial/geometry/boundingBox/maxX	
heritageAssetIdentification/	spatial/geometry/boundingBox/minY	
heritageAssetIdentification/	spatial/geometry/boundingBox/max Y	
heritageAssetIdentification/	spatial/geometry/quickpoint/x	objectIdentificationWrap/repositoryWrap/ repositorySet /repositoryLocation/gml objectIdentificationWrap/repositoryWrap/ repositorySet /repositoryLocation/partOfPlace/gml
heritageAssetIdentification/	spatial/geometry/quickpoint/y	objectIdentificationWrap/repositoryWrap/ repositorySet /repositoryLocation/gml objectIdentificationWrap/repositoryWrap/ repositorySet /repositoryLocation/partOfPlace/gml
heritageAssetIde	spatial/G	

ntification/	geometry/entity	
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heritageAssetId ntification/	spatial/geometry/height	
heritageAssetId ntification/	spatial/geometry/area	
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heritageAssetId ntification/	references/recordInformation/type	
heritageAssetId ntification/	references/recordInformation/source	
heritageAssetId ntification/	references/recordInformation/country	
heritageAssetId ntification/	references/recordInformation/creation/actor/id	
heritageAssetId ntification/	references/recordInformation/creation/actor/name	
heritageAssetId ntification/	references/recordInformation/creation/actor/actorType	
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heritageAssetId ntification/	references/recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/name	
heritageAssetId ntification/	references/recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/role	

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heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/creation/actor/vitalDates/deathDate	
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heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/update/actor/id	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/update/actor/name	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/update/actor/actorType	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/update/actor/roles	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/name	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/role	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/organization	
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heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/address/country	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/phone	
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heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/email	
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heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/update/actor/placeOfDeath	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/update/actor/placeOfActivity	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/update/actor/biographicalNote	

heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/update/date	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/language	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/rights/copyright/rightsHolder	recordWrap/recordRights/rightsHolder/legalBodyName/appellationValue
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/rights/copyright/rightsDates	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/rights/copyright/creditLine	recordWrap/recordRights/creditLine
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/rights/accessRights/grantedTo	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/rights/accessRights/conditions	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/rights/accessRights/dateFrom	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/rights/accessRights/dateTo	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/rights/accessRights/statement	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/statement	recordWrap/recordRights/creditLine
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heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/role	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/organization	
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heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/postCodeOrZipCode	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/locality	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/adminArea	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/country	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/phone	
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heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/email	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/fees	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/recordInformation/keywords	
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heritageAssetIdentification/	references/appellation/name	resourceWrap/resourceSet/resourceRepresentation/ linkResource

heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/id	resourceWrap/resourceSet/resourceSource/legalBodyID
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/name	resourceWrap /resourceSet/resourceSource/legalBodyName/appellationValue
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/actorType	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/roles	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/contacts/name	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/contacts/roles	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/contacts/organization	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/contacts/address/buildingName	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/contacts/address/NumberInRoad	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/contacts/address/roadName	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/contacts/address/townOrCity	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/contacts/address/postcodeOrZipcode	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/contacts/address/locality	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/contacts/address/adminArea	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/contacts/address/country	

notification/		
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heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/placeOfBirth	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/placeOfDeath	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/placeOfActivity	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/biographicalNote	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/vitalDates/birthDate	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/vitalDates/deatDate	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/vitalDates/type	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/placeOfBirth	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/placeOfDeath	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/placeOfActivity	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/actors/biographicalNotes	

notification/		
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heritageAssetIdentification/	references/subject	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/copyright/rightsHolder	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/copyright/rightsDates	resourceWrap/resourceSet/rightsResource/rightsDate/earliestDate resourceWrap/resourceSet/rightsResource/rightsDate/latestDate
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/copyright/creditLine	resourceWrap/resourceSet/rightsResource/creditLine
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/accessRights/grantedTo	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/accessRights/conditions	resourceWrap/resourceSet/rightsResource/creditLine
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/accessRights/dateFrom	resourceWrap/resourceSet/rightsResource/rightsDate/earliestDate
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/accessRights/dateTo	resourceWrap/resourceSet/rightsResource/rightsDate/latestDate
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heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/reproductionRights/statement	

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heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/reproductionRights/contactsrole	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/organization	resourceWrap/resourceSet/rightsResource/rightsHolder/legalBodyName/appellationValue
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/buildingName	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/NumberInRoad	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/roadName	
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heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/locality	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/adminArea	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/country	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/phone	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/fax	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/email	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/reproductionRights/Fees	

notification/		
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heritageAssetIdentification/	references/publicationStatement/placeOfPublication	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/publicationStatement/date	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/note	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/relations/ Appellation/name	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/relations/ Appellation/id	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/relations/typeOfRelation	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/relations/targetOfRelation	
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heritageAssetIdentification/	relations/Appellation/id	
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heritageAssetIdentification/	relations/targetOfRelation	
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digitalResource/	recordInformation/source	

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digitalResource/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/role	
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digitalResource/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/address/country	
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digitalResource/	recordInformation/creation/actor/placeOfDeath	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/creation/actor/placeOfActivity	
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digitalResource/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/address/townOrCity	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/address/postcodeOrZipcode	

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digitalResource/	recordInformation/update/actors/contacts/address/country	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/phone	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/fax	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/email	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/update/actor/vitalDates/birthDate	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/update/actor/vitalDates/deathDate	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/update/actor/vitalDates/type	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/update/actor/placeOfBirth	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/update/actor/placeOfDeath	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/update/actor/placeOfActivity	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/update/actor/biographicalNote	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/update/date	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/language	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/copyright/rightsHolder	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/copyright/rightsDates	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/copyright/creditLine	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/accessRights/grantedTo	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/accessRights/conditions	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/accessRights/dateFrom	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/accessRights/dateTo	

digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/accessRights/statement	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/statement	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/name	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/role	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/organization	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/buildingName	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/NumberInRoad	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/roadName	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/townOrCity	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/postcodeOrZipcode	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/locality	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/adminArea	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/country	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/phone	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/fax	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/email	
digitalResource/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/Fees	
digitalResource/	recordInformation//keywords	
digitalResource/	appellation/name	resourceWrap /resourceSet/resourceRepresentation/

		linkResource
digitalResource/	appellation/id	resourceWrap/ resourceSet/resourceID
digitalResource/	actors/id	resourceWrap/resourceSet/resourceSource/legalBodyID
digitalResource/	actors/name	resourceWrap/resourceSet/resourceSource/legalBodyName/appellationValue
digitalResource/	actors/actorType	
digitalResource/	actors/roles	
digitalResource/	actors/contacts/name	
digitalResource/	actors/contacts/role	
digitalResource/	actors/contacts/organization	
digitalResource/	actors/contacts/address/buildingName	
digitalResource/	actors/contacts/address/NumberInRoad	
digitalResource/	actors/contacts/address/roadName	
digitalResource/	actors/contacts/address/townOrCity	
digitalResource/	actors/contacts/address/postcodeOrZipcode	
digitalResource/	actors/contacts/address/locality	
digitalResource/	actors/contacts/address/adminArea	
digitalResource/	actors/contacts/address/country	
digitalResource/	actors/contacts/phone	
digitalResource/	actors/contacts/fax	
digitalResource/	actors/contacts/email	
digitalResource/	actors/vitalDates/birthDate	
digitalResource/	actors/vitalDates/deathDate	
digitalResource/	actors/vitalDates/type	
digitalResource/	actors/placeOfBirth	
digitalResource/	actors/placeOfDeath	

digitalResource/	actors/placeOfActivity	
digitalResource/	actors/biographicalNote	
digitalResource/	Format	resourceWrap/resourceSet/resourcePerspective/term
digitalResource/	formatDetails	
digitalResource/	Medium	resourceWrap/resourceSet/resourceType/term
digitalResource/	Extent	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/namedLocation	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/address/buildingName	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/address/NumberInRoad	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/address/roadName	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/address/townOrCity	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/address/postcodeOrZipcode	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/address/locality	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/address/adminArea	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/address/coconut	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/geopoliticalArea	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/geopoliticalAreaType	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/cadastralReference	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/spatialReferenceSystem	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/cartographicReference/spatialFeatureType	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/cartographicReference/coordinates/x	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/cartographicReference/coordinates/y	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/cartographicReference/coordinates/z	

digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/geometry/boundingBox/minx	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/geometry/boundingBox/maxX	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/geometry/boundingBox/minY	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/geometry/boundingBox/maxY	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/geometry/quickpoint/x	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/geometry/quickpoint/y	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/geometry/entity	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/geometry/storedPrecision	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/geometry/height	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/geometry/area	
digitalResource/	spatial/locationSet/representation	
digitalResource/	Subject	
digitalResource/	temporal/timeSpan/startDate	resourceWrap /resourceSet/date/earliestDate
digitalResource/	temporal/timeSpan/endDate	resourceWrap /resourceSet/date/ latestDate
digitalResource/	temporal/timeSpan/dimension	
digitalResource/	temporal/timeSpan/dateRangeQualifier	
digitalResource/	temporal/periodName	resourceWrap /resourceSet/displayDate
digitalResource/	temporal/displayDate	resourceWrap /resourceSet/displayDate
digitalResource/	temporal/scientificDate	
digitalResource/	temporal/scientificDateMethod	
digitalResource/	publicationstatement/publisher	
digitalResource/	publicationstatement/placeOfPublication	
digitalResource/	publicationstatement/date	resourceWrap /resourceSet/displayDate
digitalResource/	Type	resourceWrap /resourceSet/resourceType/term

digitalResource/	Description	resourceWrap /resourceSet/resourceDescription
digitalResource/	Note	
digitalResource/	Created	
digitalResource/	Provenance	
digitalResource/	Language	
digitalResource/	Link	resourceWrap/resourceSet/resourceRepresentation/ linkResource
digitalResource/	Object	
digitalResource/	isShownAt	
digitalResource/	resourceMetadataLocation	
digitalResource/	relations/Appellation	
digitalResource/	relations/typeOfRelation	
digitalResource/	relations/targetOfRelation	
digitalResource/	rights/copyright/rightsHolder	resourceWrap/resourceSet/rightsResource/rightsHolder/legalBodyName/a ppellationValue
digitalResource/	rights/copyright/rightsDates	resourceWrap/resourceSet/rightsResource/rightsDate/ earliestDate resourceWrap/resourceSet/rightsResource/rightsDate/ latestDate
digitalResource/	rights/copyright/creditLine	resourceWrap/resourceSet/rightsResource/creditLine
digitalResource/	rights/accessRights/grantedTo	
digitalResource/	rights/accessRights/Conditions	resourceWrap/resourceSet/rightsResource/creditLine
digitalResource/	rights/accessRights/dateFrom	
digitalResource/	rights/accessRights/dateTo	resourceWrap/resourceSet/rightsResource/rightsDate/ latestDate
digitalResource/	rights/accessRights/statement	resourceWrap/resourceSet/rightsResource/creditLine

digitalResource/	rights/reproductionRights/statement	resourceWrap/resourceSet/rightsResource/creditLine
digitalResource/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/name	
digitalResource/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/role	
digitalResource/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/organization	
digitalResource/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/buildingName	
digitalResource/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/NumberInRoad	
digitalResource/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/roadName	
digitalResource/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/townOrCity	
digitalResource/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/postcodeOrZipcode	
digitalResource/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/locality	
digitalResource/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/adminArea	
digitalResource/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/country	
digitalResource/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/phone	
digitalResource/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/fax	
digitalResource/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/email	
digitalResource/	rights/reproductionRights/Fees	
digitalResource/	rights/reproductionRights/licence	
activity/	recordInformation/id	
	recordInformation/type	
activity/	recordInformation/source	
activity/	recordInformation/country	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/actor/id	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/actor/name	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/actor/actorType	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/actor/roles	

activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/actor/contacts/name	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/role	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/ actor/contacts/organization	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/ contacts/address/buildingName	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/ actor/contacts/address/NumberInRoad	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/address/roadName	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/address/townOrCity	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/address/postcode OrZipcode	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/actor/contacts/address/locality	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/address/adminArea	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/address/country	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/phone	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/fax	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/contacts/email	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/vitalDates/birthDate	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/vitalDates/deathDate	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/vitalDates/type	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/placeOfBirth	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/actor/placeOfDeath	

activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/placeOfActivity	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/actor/biographicalNote	
activity/	recordInformation/creation/date	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/id	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/name	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/actorType	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/roles	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/name	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/role	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/organization	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/address/buildingName	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/address/NumberInRoad	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/address/roadName	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/address/townOrCity	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/address/postcodeOrZipcode	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/address/locality	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/address/adminArea	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/address/country	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/phone	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/fax	

activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/contacts/email	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/vitalDates/birthDate	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/vitalDates/deathDate	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/vitalDates/type	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/placeOfBirth	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/placeOfDeath	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/placeOfActivity	
activity/	recordInformation/update/actor/biographicalNote	
activity/	recordInformation/update/date	
activity/	recordInformation/language	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/copyright/rightsHolder	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/copyright/rightsDates	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/copyright/creditLine	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/accessRights/grantedTo	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/accessRights/Conditions	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/accessRights/dateFrom	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/accessRights/dateTo	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/accessRights/statement	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/statement	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/name	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/role	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/organization	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/buildingName	

activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/addresses/NumberInRoad	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/addresses/roadName	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/addresses/townOrCity	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/addresses/postcodeOrZipcode	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/addresses/locality	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/addresses/adminArea	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/addresses/country	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/phone	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/fax	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/email	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/fees	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/licence	
activity/	appellation/name	eventWrap/ eventSet/event/roleInEvent/term eventWrap/ eventSet/event/eventName/appellationValue
activity/	appellation/id	
activity/	description/	eventWrap/eventSet/event/eventDescriptionSet/ descriptiveNoteValue
activity/	actors/id	eventWrap/eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/actorID
activity/	actors/name	eventWrap/eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/nameActorSet/ap

		pellationValue
activity/	actors/actorType	
activity/	actors/roles	
activity/	actors/contacts/name	
activity/	actors/contacts/role	
activity/	actors/contacts/organization	
activity/	actors/contacts/address/buildingName	
activity/	actors/contacts/address/NumberInRoad	
activity/	actors/contacts/address/roadName	
activity/	actors/contacts/address/townOrCity	
activity/	actors/contacts/address/postcodeOrZipcode	
activity/	actors/contacts/address/locality	
activity/	actors/contacts/address/adminArea	
activity/	actors/contacts/address/country	
activity/	actors/contacts/phone	
activity/	actors/contacts/fax	
activity/	actors/contacts/email	
activity/	actors/vitalDates/birthDate	eventWrap/ eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/vitalDatesActor/earliestDate eventWrap/ eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/vitalDatesActor/latestDate
activity/	actors/vitalDates/deathDate	
activity/	actors/vitalDates/type	
activity/	actors/placeOfBirth	eventWrap/ eventSet/event/eventActor/actorInRole/actor/nationalityActor/term
activity/	actors/placeOfDeath	
activity/	actors/placeOfActivity	
activity/	actors/biographicalNote	

activity/	EventType	eventWrap/ eventSet/event/eventType/term
activity/	temporal/timeSpan/startDate	eventWrap/eventSet/event/eventDate/Date/earliestDate
activity/	temporal/timeSpan/endDate	eventWrap/eventSet/event/Date/latestDate
activity/	temporal/timeSpan/dimension	
activity/	temporal/timeSpan/dateRangeQualifier	
activity/	temporal/periodName	eventWrap/eventSet/event/periodName/Term
activity/	temporal/displayDate	eventWrap/eventSet/event/eventDate/displayDate
activity/	spatial/locationSet/namedLocation	eventWrap/eventSet/event/eventPlace/place/ namePlaceSet/appellationValue
activity/	spatial/locationSet/address/buildingName	
activity/	spatial/locationSet/address/NumberInRoad	
activity/	spatial/locationSet/address/roadName	
activity/	spatial/locationSet/address/townOrCity	
activity/	spatial/locationSet/address/postcodeOrZipcode	
activity/	spatial/locationSet/address/locality	
activity/	spatial/locationSet/address/adminArea	
activity/	spatial/locationSet/address/coconut	
activity/	spatial/locationSet/geopoliticalArea	
activity/	spatial/locationSet/geopoliticalAreaType	
activity/	spatial/locationSet/cadastralReference	
activity/	spatial/locationSet/historicalname	
activity/	spatial/spatialReferenceSystem	
activity/	spatial/cartographicReference/spatialFeatureType	
activity/	spatial/cartographicReference/coordinates/x	
activity/	spatial/cartographicReference/coordinates/y	
activity/	spatial/cartographicReference/coordinates/z	
activity/	spatial/geometry/boundingBox/minx	
activity/	spatial/geometry/boundingBox/maxX	

activity/	spatial/geometry/boundingBox/minY	
activity/	spatial/geometry/boundingBox/maxY	
activity/	spatial/geometry/quickPoint/x	
activity/	spatial/geometry/quickPoint/y	
activity/	spatial/geometry/entity	
activity/	spatial/geometry/storedPrecision	
activity/	spatial/geometry/height	
activity/	spatial/geometry/area	
activity/	spatial/representations	
activity/	assessments/Term	
activity/	eventMethod	
activity/	materialsAndTechniques	
activity/	relations/Appellation	
activity/	relations/typeOfRelation	
activity/	Relations/targetOfRelation	

D2.2.3 3.3

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CARARE- DC (ESE) metadata mapping

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Authors:

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Dissemination Level		
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C	Confidential, only for members of the consortium and the Commission Services	

Revision History

Revision	Date	Author	Organisation	Description
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3.3 CARARE- DC (ESE) metadata mapping

Dublin Core is a standard for cross-domain information resource description. Its name “Dublin” is due to its origin at a 1995 invitational workshop in Dublin, Ohio, while “core” because its elements are broad and generic, usable for describing a wide range of resources. It provides a simple and standardised set of conventions for describing things online in a machine understandable way making them easier to find. Dublin Core is a metadata standard used mainly to describe content of multimedia essence, such as video, sound, image, text and composite media. Early Dublin Core workshops popularized the idea of "core metadata" for simple and generic resource descriptions. Dublin Core achieved wide dissemination as part of the Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) and has been ratified as IETF RFC 5013, ANSI/NISO Standard Z39.85-2007, and ISO Standard 15836:2009.

Starting in 2000, the Dublin Core community focused on "application profiles", the idea that metadata records would use Dublin Core together with other specialized vocabularies to meet particular implementation requirements. During that time, the World Wide Web Consortium's work on a generic data model for metadata, the Resource Description Framework (RDF), was maturing. As part of an extended set of DCMI Metadata Terms, Dublin Core became one of most popular vocabularies for use with RDF, more recently in the context of the Linked Data movement.

The consolidation of RDF motivated an effort to translate the mixed-vocabulary metadata style of the Dublin Core community into an RDF-compatible DCMI Abstract Model (2005). The DCMI Abstract Model was designed to bridge the modern paradigm of unbounded, linked data graphs with the more familiar paradigm of validatable metadata records like those used in OAI-PMH. A draft Description Set Profile specification defines a language for expressing constraints in a generic, application-independent way. The Singapore Framework for Dublin Core Application Profiles defines a set of descriptive components useful for documenting an application profile for maximum reusability.

The Dublin Core metadata standard includes two levels: Simple and Qualified. Simple Dublin Core, also known as Dublin Core Metadata Element set, is a vocabulary of fifteen properties for use in resource description. Qualified Dublin Core is an ongoing process to develop exemplary terms extending or refining the Dublin Core Metadata Element set. There exist two broad classes of qualifiers. These are Element Refinement and Encoding Scheme.

- Element Refinement: makes the meaning of an element narrower or more specific. A refined element shares the meaning of the unqualified element but with a more restricted scope. A client that does not understand a specific element refinement term should be able to ignore the qualifier and treat the metadata value as if it were an unqualified element.
- Encoding Scheme: identifies schemes that aid in the interpretation of an element value with the help of controlled vocabularies and formal notations or parsing rules. If an encoding scheme is not understood by a client or agent the value may still be useful to a human reader.

The Dublin Core metadata standard can be encoded in many syntax formats such as XML and RDF/XML. When considering an appropriate syntax, it is important to note that Dublin Core concepts and semantics are designed to be syntax independent and are equally applicable in a variety of contexts, as long as the metadata is in a form suitable for interpretation both by search engines and by human beings. We present the following terminology concerning XML, RDF/XML and Dublin Core:

- Resource: anything that has identity. Familiar examples include an electronic document, an image, a service and a collection of other resources. Not all resources are network "retrievable"; e.g., human beings, corporations, and bound books in a library can also be considered resources.
- Property: a specific aspect, characteristic, attribute, or relation used to describe a resource.
- Record: some structured metadata about a resource, comprising one or more properties and their associated values.

Dublin Core XML

One of the many syntax forms Dublin Core can be encoded in is XML. XML provides a very simple framework for the encoding of Dublin Core Elements. In the following we provide some simple rules regarding the XML syntax. These as well as recommendations, guidelines and examples for XML implementations can be found in <http://dublincore.org/documents/dc-xml-guidelines/index.shtml>.

A Dublin Core record is made up of one or more properties and their associated values. Each property is an attribute of the resource being described and can be either one of the simple elements or one of the qualified elements and may be repeated. Moreover each value is a literal string and may be associated to an encoding scheme, which always has a name. Finally each literal string value may have an associated language (e.g. en-GB).

Dublin Core in Ontology Definition Languages

Although XML provides a very simple framework for encoding Dublin Core elements its abstract syntax does not provide semantics to the content described. Taking into account that cultural heritage are mostly indexed on the basis of divergent metadata standards, that hampers the combination and opening up of the cultural content a more semantic language needs to be supported by Dublin Core. This is why Dublin Core can be encoded in Ontology Definition Language. RDF and OWL provide semantics making interoperability easier among knowledge bases. Moreover, through some tools provides reasoning such as checking the consistency and validity of metadata as well as extracting implicit from explicit knowledge.

Unlike the XML syntax, in the RDF/XML case there is a different syntax regarding unqualified and qualified elements. Representing unqualified Dublin Core elements requires a bit more extra information. Every assertion is made about a fixed resource. Each resource is identified between a pair of rdf:Description tags.

CROSSWALK TABLE BETWEEN CARARE AND DC

CARARE	DC
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collectionInformation/	title	DC title http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/title
collectionInformation/	keywords	DC subject http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/subject
collectionInformation/	contacts/name	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/publisher
collectionInformation/	contacts/role	
collectionInformation/	contacts/organization	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/publisher
collectionInformation/	contacts/address/buildingName	
collectionInformation/	contacts/address/numberInRoad	
collectionInformation/	contacts/address/roadname	
collectionInformation/	contacts/address/townOrCity	
collectionInformation/	contacts/address/postcodeOrZipcode	
collectionInformation/	contacts/address/locality	
collectionInformation/	contacts/address/adminArea	
collectionInformation/	contacts/address/country	
collectionInformation/	contacts/phone	
collectionInformation/	contacts/fax	

n/		
collectionInformation/	contacts/email	
collectionInformation/	rights/copyright/rightsHolder	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/rights http://purl.org/dc/terms/rightsHolder
collectionInformation/	rights/copyright/rightsDates	http://purl.org/dc/terms/dateCopyrighted
collectionInformation/	rights/copyright/creditLine	DC rights http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/rights
collectionInformation/	rights/accessRights/grantedTo	
collectionInformation/	rights/accessRights/conditions	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/rights
collectionInformation/	rights/accessRights/dateFrom	http://purl.org/dc/terms/issued
collectionInformation/	rights/accessRights/dateTo	
collectionInformation/	rights/accessRights/statement	DC rights http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/rights
collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/statement	DC rights http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/rights
collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/name	http://purl.org/dc/terms/rightsHolder
collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/role	
collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/organization	http://purl.org/dc/terms/rightsHolder
collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/buildingName	
collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/	

collectionInformation/	address/numberInRoad	
collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/ address/roadname	
collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/ address/townOrCity	
collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/ address/postcodeOrZipcode	
collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/ address/locality	
collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/ address/adminArea	
collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/ address/country	
collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/ phone	
collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/ fax	
collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/contacts/ email	
collectionInformation/	rights/reproductionRights/fees	
collectionInformation/	rights/licence	DC rights http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/rights
collectionInformation/	Source	
collectionInformation/	language	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/language
collectionInformation/	statement	

collectionInformation/	creation/createdOn	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/date
collectionInformation/	creation/query	
collectionInformation/	coverage/temporal	DC Coverage http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/coverage http://purl.org/dc/terms/temporal
collectionInformation/	coverage/temporal/timeSpan/startDate	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/coverage http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/date http://purl.org/dc/terms/temporal
collectionInformation/	coverage/temporal/timeSpan/endDate	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/coverage http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/date http://purl.org/dc/terms/temporal
collectionInformation/	coverage/temporal/timeSpan/dimension	
collectionInformation/	coverage/temporal/timeSpan/dateRangeQualifier	
collectionInformation/	coverage/temporal/periodname	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/coverage http://purl.org/dc/terms/temporal
collectionInformation/	coverage/temporal/displayDate	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/coverage http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/date http://purl.org/dc/terms/temporal
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/coverage http://purl.org/dc/terms/spatial
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/locationSet/GeopoliticalArea	http://purl.org/dc/terms/spatial
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/locationSet/GeopoliticalAreaType	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/locationSet/namedLocation	http://purl.org/dc/terms/spatial
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/locationSet/address/buildingName	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/locationSet/address	

information/	/NumberInRoad	
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collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/locationSet/address/postcodeOrZipcode	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/locationSet/address/locality	http://purl.org/dc/terms/spatial
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/locationSet/address/adminArea	http://purl.org/dc/terms/spatial
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/locationSet/address/country	http://purl.org/dc/terms/spatial
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/locationSet/GeopoliticalArea	http://purl.org/dc/terms/spatial
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/locationSet/geopoliticalAreaType	
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collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/locationSet/historicalname	http://purl.org/dc/terms/spatial
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/locationSet/spatialReferenceSystem	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/cartographicReference/spatialFeatureType	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/cartographicReference/coordinates/x	DC Coverage http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/coverage http://purl.org/dc/terms/spatial
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/cartographicReference/coordinates/y	DC Coverage http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/coverage http://purl.org/dc/terms/spatial

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collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/geometry/boundingBox/minx	
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collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/geometry/area	
collectionInformation/	coverage/spatial/representations	
collectionInformation/	spatialReferenceSystem	
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heritageAssetIdentifi	recordInformation/type	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/type

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heritageAs setIdentifi cation/	recordInformation/creation/actor/act orType	
heritageAs setIdentifi cation/	recordInformation/creation/actor/ roles	
heritageAs setIdentifi cation/	recordInformation/creation/actor/ contacts/name	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/creator http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/contributor http://purl.org/dc/terms/rightsHolder
heritageAs setIdentifi cation/	recordInformation/creation/actor/ contacts/role	
heritageAs setIdentifi cation/	recordInformation/creation/actor/ contacts/organization	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/creator http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/contributor http://purl.org/dc/terms/rightsHolder
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heritageAs setIdentifi cation/	recordInformation/creation/actor/co ntacts /address/postcodeOrZipcode	

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heritageAs setIdentifi cation/	recordInformation/creation/actor/ vitalDates/deathDate	
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heritageAs setIdentifi cation/ contacts/organization	recordInformation/update/actor/ contacts/organization	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/creator http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/contributor http://purl.org/dc/terms/rightsHolder
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heritageAs setIdentification/	references/actors/actorType	
heritageAs setIdentification/	references/actors/roles	
heritageAs setIdentification/	references/actors/contacts/name	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/creator http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/contributor http://purl.org/dc/terms/rightsHolder

heritageAs setIdentifi cation/	references/actors/contacts/roles	
heritageAs setIdentifi cation/	references/actors/contacts/organizati on	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/creator http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/contributor http://purl.org/dc/terms/rightsHolder
heritageAs setIdentifi cation/	references/actors/contacts/address/ buildingName	
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heritageAs setIdentifi cation/	references/actors/contacts/address/ roadName	
heritageAs setIdentifi cation/	references/actors/contacts/address/ townOrCity	
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heritageAs setIdentifi cation/	references/actors/contacts/address/ country	
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heritageAs setIdentifi	references/actors/placeOfBirth	

heritageAs setIdentification/	references/actors/placeOfDeath	
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heritageAs setIdentification/	references/actors/vitalDates/deathDate	
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heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/role	
heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/organization	http://purl.org/dc/terms/rightsHolder
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heritageAssetIdentification/	references/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/roadName	

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digitalRes ource/	recordInformation/creation/actor/na me	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/creator DC contributor http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/contributor
digitalRes ource/	recordInformation/creation/actor/ actorType	
digitalRes ource/	recordInformation/creation/actor/ roles	
digitalRes ource/	recordInformation/creation/actor/ contacts/name	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/creator http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/contributor http://purl.org/dc/terms/rightsHolder
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source/	phone	
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activity/	recordInformation/rights/access Rights/statement	DC rights http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/rights
activity/	recordInformation/rights/ reproductionRights/statement	DC rights http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/rights
activity/	recordInformation/rights/ reproductionRights/contacts/name	http://purl.org/dc/terms/rightsHolder
activity/	recordInformation/rights/ reproductionRights/contacts/role	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproducti onRights/contacts/organization	http://purl.org/dc/terms/rightsHolder
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproducti onRights/contacts/address/building Name	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproducti onRights/contacts/address/NumberI nRoad	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproducti onRights/contacts/address/ roadName	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproducti onRights/contacts/address/ townOrCity	

activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/postcodeOrZipcode	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/locality	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/adminArea	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/address/country	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/phone	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/fax	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/contacts/email	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/fees	
activity/	recordInformation/rights/reproductionRights/licence	DC rights http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/rights
activity/	appellation/name	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/title
activity/	appellation/id	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/identifier
activity/	description/	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/description
activity/	actors/id	
activity/	actors/name	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/creator http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/contributor
activity/	actors/actorType	
activity/	actors/roles	
activity/	actors/contacts/name	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/creator http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/contributor http://purl.org/dc/terms/rightsHolder
activity/	actors/contacts/role	
activity/	actors/contacts/organization	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/creator http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/contributor http://purl.org/dc/terms/rightsHolder
activity/	actors/contacts/address/buildingName	
activity/	actors/contacts/address/	

	NumberInRoad	
activity/	actors/contacts/address/roadName	
activity/	actors/contacts/address/townOrCity	
activity/	actors/contacts/address/postcodeOr Zipcode	
activity/	actors/contacts/address/locality	
activity/	actors/contacts/address/adminArea	
activity/	actors/contacts/address/country	
activity/	actors/contacts/phone	
activity/	actors/contacts/fax	
activity/	actors/contacts/email	
activity/	actors/vitalDates/birthDate	
activity/	actors/vitalDates/deathDate	
activity/	actors/vitalDates/type	
activity/	actors/placeOfBirth	
activity/	actors/placeOfDeath	
activity/	actors/placeOfActivity	
activity/	actors/biographicalNote	
activity/	EventType	DC type http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/type
activity/	temporal/timeSpan/startDate	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/date http://purl.org/dc/terms/temporal
activity/	temporal/timeSpan/endDate	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/date http://purl.org/dc/terms/temporal
activity/	temporal/timeSpan/dimension	
activity/	temporal/timeSpan/dateRange Qualifier	
activity/	temporal/periodName	http://purl.org/dc/terms/temporal
activity/	temporal/displayDate	http://purl.org/dc/terms/temporal
activity/	spatial/locationSet/namedLocation	http://purl.org/dc/terms/spatial
activity/	spatial/locationSet/address/building Name	
activity/	spatial/locationSet/address/Number InRoad	
activity/	spatial/locationSet/address/ roadName	
activity/	spatial/locationSet/address/ townOrCity	http://purl.org/dc/terms/spatial

activity/	spatial/locationSet/address/postcode OrZipcode	
activity/	spatial/locationSet/address/locality	http://purl.org/dc/terms/spatial
activity/	spatial/locationSet/address/ adminArea	http://purl.org/dc/terms/spatial
activity/	spatial/locationSet/address/country	http://purl.org/dc/terms/spatial
activity/	spatial/locationSet/geopoliticalArea	http://purl.org/dc/terms/spatial
activity/	spatial/locationSet/geopoliticalArea Type	
activity/	spatial/locationSet/ cadastralReference	
activity/	spatial/locationSet/historicalname	http://purl.org/dc/terms/spatial
activity/	spatial/spatialReferenceSystem	
activity/	spatial/cartographicReference/ spatialFeatureType	
activity/	spatial/cartographicReference/ coordinates/x	
activity/	spatial/cartographicReference/ coordinates/y	
activity/	spatial/cartographicReference/ coordinates/z	
activity/	spatial/geometry/boundingBox/minx	
activity/	spatial/geometry/boundingBox/max X	
activity/	spatial/geometry/boundingBox/min Y	
activity/	spatial/geometry/boundingBox/max Y	
activity/	spatial/geometry/quickPoint/x	
activity/	spatial/geometry/quickPoint/y	
activity/	spatial/geometry/entity	
activity/	spatial/geometry/storedPrecision	
activity/	spatial/geometry/height	
activity/	spatial/geometry/area	
activity/	spatial/representations	
activity/	assessments	
activity/	eventMethod	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/subject
activity/	materialsAndTechniques	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/subject
activity/	relations/Appellation	http://purl.org/dc/elements/1.1/relation

activity/	relations/typeOfRelation	
activity/	Relations/targetOfRelation	

D2.2.3 3.4

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EDM – CARARE metadata mapping

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Revision History

Revision	Date	Author	Organisation	Description
0.1	20.12.10	Christos Papatheodorou, Constantina Kakali, Giannis Tsakonas	DCU	First draft
0.2	03.01.2011	Christos Papatheodorou	DCU	Based on Kate Fernie's review

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3.4 CARARE Metadata Schema to the Europeana Data Model crosswalk

The following table describes the mapping of the CARARE Schema elements to EDM 5.2. Since EDM is a conceptual model the CARARE Elements are mapped either directly to EDM Classes and ESE elements, or to particular EDM paths.

The notation used is as follows:

- Mapping to EDM classes (and their subclasses) and elements: Class/subclass/Element
- Mapping to EDM paths: Sequences of (Class/subclass/Element -> EDM Property -> Class/subclass/Element)

Comments are given where appropriate to highlight items of interest. These comments can also be a placeholder for further details about the implementation of the mapping.

We consider that a monument is an instance of the EDM class Physical Thing. A monument is identified by a set of particular characteristics that refer to its nature, location, related events, etc. Thus these characteristics are grouped under the class Physical Thing.

Moreover there exists one more entity, the information that a monument (or a collection) carries, which is an instance of the class Europeana Object. This information could be either textual metadata (such as title, etc.), thumbnails and other digital objects related to the monument. These two entities are correlated by the paths: Physical Thing -> Realizes of -> Europeana Object and Europeana Object -> Is Representation of -> Physical Thing.

Regarding several CARARE elements carrying spatial information we need to agree with Europeana a strategy for handling spatial references.

Carare Elements	EDM Classes and Paths
Collection Information	ORE Aggregation -and- ORE Aggregation -> Provider -> CARARE-Digital Curation Unit
Comment: We need an ID for a collection and an ID for the proxy.	
Collection Information/Title	ORE Aggregation/Europeana Aggregation/DC Title
Comment: <i>Collection Information/Title@xml:lang</i> is mapped to <i>ORE Aggregation/Europeana Aggregation/Language</i> .	
Collection Information/Keywords	ORE Aggregation /DC Subject
Collection Information/Contacts	ORE Aggregation -> Data Provider -> Agent -and- ORE Proxy -> Current Location -> Place
Collection Information/Rights	ORE Aggregation/DC Rights
Collection Information/Source	ORE Proxy -> ORE Proxy In -> ORE Aggregation -> Data Provider -> Agent/DC Title -and- ORE Aggregation -> Landing Page -> Web Resource
Comment: According to EDM, we need an ID for each provider for the <i>ORE Proxy:= Agent</i> field.	
Collection Information/Language	ORE Aggregation/Language
Collection Information/Statement	ORE Aggregation/DC Description
Collection Information/Creation	ORE Aggregation/ DCTERMS Provenance
Comment: CARARE schema has not a clear statement for the custody of a collection. We could follow the practice suggested by the mapping.	
Collection Information/Creation/Created on	ORE Aggregation/Time Span/DC Terms Created
Collection Information/Creation/Query	ORE Proxy
Collection Information/Coverage/Spatial	Place/ DCTERMS Spatial

Collection Information/Coverage/Temporal	Time Span/DC Coverage
Collection Information/Spatial Reference System	Place/DCTERMS Spatial
Heritage Asset Identification/Record Information /ID	RDFS:Resource/Physical Thing/DC Identifier -> is ORE Aggregates -> ORE Aggregation -> ORE Proxy In -> ORE Proxy -> ORE Proxy For -> Europeana Object/DC Identifier
Heritage Asset Identification/Appellation/Name	Europeana Object/DC Title
Heritage Asset Identification/Appellation/ID	Physical Thing /DC Identifier
Heritage Asset Identification/Description	Physical Thing/DC Description
Heritage Asset Identification/Actors	Agent -> Was Present At -> Event -> Was Present At -> Physical Thing -and- Europeana Object/Provider:= CARARE - Digital Curation Unit
Comment: Repeatable path according to the role of the Actors.	
Heritage Asset Identification/Actors/Name	Agent/DC Creator -> Was Present At -> Event -> Was Present At -> Physical Thing -or- Agent/DC Contributor -> Was Present At -> Event -> Was Present At -> Physical Thing -or- Agent/ DCTERMS Provenance
Comment: If Actor/Roles <> (creator and custodian) then Heritage asset Identification/Actors/Name maps to Physical Thing /Agent/DC Contributor. If Actor/Roles = custodian then Heritage asset Identification/Actors/Name maps to Physical Thing /Agent/DCTERMS Provenance.	
Heritage Asset Identification/Designations/Protection type	Physical Thing/DC Description
Heritage Asset Identification/Designations/Grade	Physical Thing/DC Description
Heritage Asset Identification/Designations/Date from	mapping not feasible
Heritage Asset Identification/Designations/Date to	mapping not feasible
Heritage Asset Identification/Conditions/Condition	Physical Thing/DC Description

Heritage Asset Identification/Conditions/Condition Assessment		Physical Thing/DC Description -> Has Met -> Event -> Has Type -> Type:=Condition Assessment
Heritage Asset Identification/Conditions/Condition Date		Physical Thing -> Has Met -> Event -> Occurred At -> Time Span and Physical Thing -> Has Met -> Event -> Has Type -> Type:=Condition Assessment
Heritage Asset Identification/Conditions/Relations		Physical Thing -> Has Met -> Event
Heritage Asset Identification/Characters/Heritage asset type		Physical Thing -> Has Type -> Type
Heritage Asset Identification/Characters/Temporal		Physical Thing -> Was Present At -> Event -> Occurred At -> Time Span
Heritage Asset Identification/Characters/Materials		Physical Thing/ DCTERMS Medium
Heritage Asset Identification/Characters/Dimensions		Physical Thing/ DCTERMS Extent
Heritage Asset Identification/Characters/Craft		Physical Thing -> Has Type ->Type
Heritage Asset Identification/Repository location		Physical Thing -> ORE Aggregates -> ORE Aggregation -> ORE Proxy In -> ORE Proxy -> ORE Proxy For -> Ore:Proxy -> Current Location -> Place
Heritage Asset Identification/Spatial		Physical Thing -> Was Present At -> Event -> Happened At -> Place
Heritage Asset Identification/References		Physical Thing -> DCTERMS Is Referenced By -> Information Resource
Heritage Identification/References/Record information/ID	Asset	Physical Thing -> DCTERMS Is Referenced By -> Information Resource/DC Identifier
Heritage Identification/References/Appellation	Asset	Physical Thing -> DCTERMS Is Referenced By -> Information Resource/DCTERMS References
Heritage Identification/References/Actors	asset	Physical Thing -> DCTERMS Is Referenced By -> Information Resource/DC creator
<p>Comment:</p> <p>If Actors/roles <> creator then mapped to <i>Information Resource/DC Contributor</i></p>		
Heritage Identification/References/Type	Asset	Physical Thing -> DCTERMS Is Referenced By -> Information Resource/DC Type
Heritage Asset Identification/References/Medium		Physical Thing -> DCTERMS Is Referenced By -> Information Resource/ DCTERMS Medium
Heritage Asset Identification/References/Extent		Physical Thing -> DCTERMS Is Referenced By -> Information Resource/ DCTERMS Extent

Heritage Asset Identification/References/Subject	Physical Thing -> DCTERMS Is Referenced By -> Information Resource/DC Subject
Heritage Asset Identification/References/Rights	Physical Thing -> DCTERMS Is Referenced By -> Information Resource/DC Rights
Heritage Asset Identification/References/Publication statement	Physical Thing -> DCTERMS Is Referenced By -> Information Resource/DC Publisher
Heritage Asset Identification/References/Note	Physical Thing -> DCTERMS Is Referenced By -> Information Resource/DC Description
Heritage Asset Identification/References/Relations	Physical Thing -> DCTERMS Is Referenced By -> Information Resource
Heritage Asset Identification/Relations	<p>In general:</p> <p>Europeana Object/DC Relation</p> <p>-or-</p> <p>Physical Thing/DC Relation</p> <p>In detail:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We denote the fact that a Heritage Asset is part of a collection using the path: Physical Thing -> ORE Aggregates -> ORE Aggregation/ Europeana Aggregation -> Aggregated CHO -> Europeana Object - We denote the relation of a Heritage Asset with an Event, using the path: Physical Thing -> Was Present At -> Event - We denote the relation of a Heritage Asset with a Digital Resource using the path: Europeana Object -> Is Representation Of -> Physical Thing <p>We could also use the sub-properties of the DC Relation appeared in EDM.</p>
Digital Resource	Web Resource/Europeana Object
Digital Resource/Record information/ID	ORE Proxy/DC Identifier -> ORE Proxy For -> Web Resource/Europeana Object/
Digital Resource/Appellation/Name	Web Resource/Europeana Object/DC Title
Digital Resource/Appellation/ID	Web Resource/Europeana Object/DC Identifier
Digital Resource/Actors	<p>Agent -> Was Present At -> Event -> Was Present At -> WebResource/Europeana Object</p> <p>-and-</p> <p>Europeana Object/Provider:= CARARE - Digital Curation Unit</p>
Comment:	Repeatable path according to the role of the Actors.

Digital Resource/Format	Web Resource/Europeana Object/DC Format
Digital Resource/Format Details	Web Resource/Europeana Object/DC Format
Digital Resource/Medium	Web Resource/Europeana Object/ DCTERMS Medium
Digital Resource/Extent	Web Resource/Europeana Object/ DCTERMS Extent
Digital Resource/Spatial	Web Resource/Europeana Object/DC TERMS Spatial
Digital Resource/Subject	Web Resource/Europeana Object/DC Subject
Digital Resource/Temporal	Web Resource/Europeana Object/DC TERMS Temporal
Digital Resource/Publication statement	Web Resource/Europeana Object/DC Publisher
Digital Resource/Type	Web Resource/Europeana Object/DC Type
Digital Resource/Description	Web Resource/Europeana Object/DC Description
Digital Resource/Note	Web Resource/Europeana Object/DC Description
Digital Resource/Created	Web Resource/Europeana Object/DC TERMS Created
Digital Resource/Provenance	Web Resource/Europeana Object/ DCTERMS Provenance
Digital Resource/Language	Web Resource/Europeana Object/DC Language
Digital Resource/Link	Web Resource/Europeana Object/Object
Digital Resource/IsShownAt	Web Resource/Europeana Object -> Is Shown By -> Landing Page
Digital Resource/Resource metadata location	Web Resource/Europeana Object -> Is Representation of -> Web Resource/Europeana Object -> Is Shown At -> Landing Page

Digital Resource/Relations	<p>In general: Web Resource/Europeana Object/DC Relation</p> <p>In detail:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - We denote the fact that a Digital Resource is part of a collection using the path: ORE Aggregation/Europeana Aggregation -> Aggregated CHO -> Europeana Object - We denote the relation of a Digital Resource with an Event, using the path: Europeana Object -> Was Present At -> Event - We denote the relation of a Heritage asset with a Digital Resource using the path: Europeana Object -> Is Representation Of -> Physical Thing <p>We could also use the sub-properties of the DC Relation appeared in EDM</p>
Digital Resource/Rights	Web Resource/Europeana Object/DC Rights
Relations	DC Relation
Relations/Appellation	mapping not feasible
Relations/Type of Relation	According to the CARARE vocabulary, as well as the EDM and DCTERMS vocabularies
Relations/Target of Relation	The DC Identifier of the related object
Activity	Event
Activity/Record information	Event /DC Identifier
Activity/Appellation	Event/DC Title
Activity/Description	Event/DC Description
Activity/Actors	Agent -> Was Present At -> Event
Activity/Event type	Event -> Has Type -> Type
Activity/Temporal	Event -> Happened At -> Time Span
Activity/Spatial	Event -> Occurred At -> Place
Activity/Assessments	Event/DC Description

Activity/Event method	Event/DC Description
Activity/Materials and techniques	Event/DC Description
Activity/Relations	RDFS:Resource -> Has Met -> Event
Record Information/ID	RDFS:Resource/ Information Resource /DC Identifier iff RDFS:Resource/ Information Resource -> ORE Aggregates -> ORE Aggregation -> ORE Proxy In -> ORE Proxy -> ORE Proxy For -> Europeana Object
Record Information/Type	RDFS:Resource/ Information Resource -> Has Type ->Type iff RDFS:Resource/ Information Resource -> ORE Aggregates -> ORE Aggregation -> ORE Proxy In -> ORE Proxy -> ORE Proxy For -> Europeana Object
Record Information/Source	RDFS:Resource/ Information Resource/ DCTERMS Provenance iff RDFS:Resource/ Information Resource -> ORE Aggregates -> ORE Aggregation -> ORE Proxy In -> ORE Proxy -> ORE Proxy For -> Europeana Object
Record Information/Country	RDFS:Resource/ORE Proxy/Country iff RDFS:Resource/ Information Resource -> ORE Aggregates -> ORE Aggregation -> ORE Proxy In -> ORE Proxy -> ORE Proxy For -> Europeana Object
Record Information/Creation	mapping not feasible
Record Information/Creation/Date	RDFS:Resource/ Information Resource/ DCTERMS Created iff RDFS:Resource/ Information Resource -> ORE Aggregates -> ORE Aggregation -> ORE Proxy In -> ORE Proxy -> ORE Proxy For -> Europeana Object
Record Information/Creation/Actor	RDFS:Resource/Information Resource/DC Creator iff RDFS:Resource/ Information Resource -> ORE Aggregates -> ORE Aggregation -> ORE Proxy In -> ORE Proxy -> ORE Proxy For -> Europeana Object
Record Information/Update	mapping not feasible
Record Information/Update/Date	RDFS:Resource/ Information Resource / DC Date iff RDFS:Resource/ Information Resource -> ORE Aggregates -> ORE Aggregation -> ORE Proxy In -> ORE Proxy -> ORE Proxy For -> Europeana Object

Record Information/Update/Actor	RDFS:Resource/ Information Resource /DC Contributor iff RDFS:Resource/ Information Resource -> ORE Aggregates -> ORE Aggregation -> ORE Proxy In -> ORE Proxy -> ORE Proxy For -> Europeana Object
Record Information/Language	RDFS: Resource/Information Resource/DC Language iff RDFS:Resource/ Information Resource -> ORE Aggregates -> ORE Aggregation -> ORE Proxy In -> ORE Proxy -> ORE Proxy For -> Europeana Object
Record Information/Rights	RDFS: Resource/Information Resource/DC Rights iff RDFS:Resource/ Information Resource -> ORE Aggregates -> ORE Aggregation -> ORE Proxy In -> ORE Proxy -> ORE Proxy For -> Europeana Object
Record Information/Keywords	RDFS: Resource/Information Resource/DC Subject iff RDFS:Resource/ Information Resource -> ORE Aggregates -> ORE Aggregation -> ORE Proxy In -> ORE Proxy -> ORE Proxy For -> Europeana Object
Rights/Copyright	RDFS:Resource/ DC Rights
Rights/Copyright/Rights holder	RDFS:Resource/DC Rights
Rights/Copyright/Rights dates	RDFS:Resource/DC Rights
Rights/Copyright/Credit line (statement)	RDFS:Resource/DC Rights
Rights/Access rights	RDFS:Resource/DC Rights
Rights/Access rights/Granted to	RDFS:Resource/DC Rights
Rights/Access rights/Conditions	RDFS:Resource/DC Rights
Rights/Access rights/Date from	RDFS:Resource/DC Rights
Rights/Access rights/Date to	RDFS:Resource/DC Rights
Rights/Access rights/Statement	RDFS:Resource/DC Rights
Rights/Reproduction rights	RDFS:Resource/DC Rights
Rights/Reproduction rights/Statement	RDFS:Resource/DC Rights
Rights/Reproduction rights/Contacts	RDFS:Resource/DC Rights

Rights/Reproduction rights/Fees	RDFS:Resource/DC Rights
Rights/License	RDFS:Resource/DC Rights
Appellation/Name	Agent/DC Creator Agent/DC Contributor Europeana Aggregation/DC Title Europeana Object/DC Title Event/DC Title Information Resource/DC Title Non-Information Resource/DC Title Physical Thing/DC Title Web Resource/DC Title
Comment: It depends on the roles sub-element and also the element for which the Appellation element is sub-element.	
Appellation/ID	Agent/DC Identifier Europeana Aggregation/DC Identifier Europeana Object/DC Identifier Event/DC Identifier Information Resource/DC Identifier Non-Information Resource/DC Identifier Physical Thing/DC Identifier Web Resource/DC Identifier
Dimensions	mapping not feasible
Dimensions/Measurement type	Physical Thing/DC Extent -> Has Type -> Type
Dimensions/Units	Physical Thing/ DC Extent -> Has Type -> Type
Dimensions/Scale	Physical Thing/ DC Extent -> Has Type -> Type
Dimensions/Value	Physical Thing/DC Extent
Craft/Placeofregistration	Physical Thing -> Was Present At -> Event -> Happened At -> Place and Physical Thing -> Was Present At -> Event -> Has type -> Type
Craft/Nationality	Physical Thing/Country

Craft/Constructionmethod	Physical Thing/DC Description
Craft/Propulsion	Physical Thing/DC Description -> Has Type -> Type
Craft/Lastjourneydetails	Physical Thing/DC Description
Craft/Lastjourneydetails/Departure	Physical Thing -> Was Present At -> Event -> Occurred At -> Place and Physical Thing -> Was Present At -> Event -> Has type -> Type
Craft/Lastjourneydetails/Destination	Physical Thing/ DCTERMS Spatial
Craft/Lastjourneydetails/Cargo	Physical Thing/DC Description
Craft/Lastjourneydetails/Mannerofloss	Physical Thing -> Was Present At -> Event/DC Description and Physical Thing -> Was Present At -> Event -> Has type -> Type
Craft/Lastjourneydetails/Dateofloss	Physical Thing -> Was Present At -> Event -> Happened At -> Time Span
Temporal/Time span	Time Span
Temporal/Time span/start date	Time Span/DC Date
Temporal/Time span/end date	Time Span/DC Date
Temporal/Time span/Dimension	Time Span/ DCTERMS Temporal
Temporal/Time span/Date range qualifier	Time Span/ DCTERMS Temporal
Temporal/Period name	Time Span/ DCTERMS Temporal
Temporal/Scientific Date	Time Span/DC Date
Temporal/Scientific Date Method	Time Span/ DCTERMS Temporal
Temporal/Display date	Time Span/ DCTERMS Temporal
Spatial/Location set	Place
Spatial/Location set/Named location	Place/DC Title

Spatial/Location set/Address	Place/ DCTERMS Spatial
Spatial/Location set/Geopolitical area	Place/ DCTERMS Spatial
Spatial/Location set/Geopolitical area type	Place/ DCTERMS Spatial
Spatial/Location set/Cadastral reference	Place/ DCTERMS Spatial
Spatial/Location set/Historical name	Place/DC Title
Spatial/Spatial reference system	Place/ DCTERMS Spatial
Spatial/Cartographic reference/	Place/ DCTERMS Spatial
Spatial/Cartographic reference/Spatial feature type	mapping not feasible
Spatial/Cartographic reference/Coordinates	Place/ DCTERMS Spatial
Spatial/Geometry	mapping not feasible
Spatial/Geometry/Bounding box	mapping not feasible
Spatial/Geometry/Quickpoint	mapping not feasible
Spatial/Geometry/Entity	mapping not feasible
Spatial/Geometry/Stored precision	mapping not feasible
Spatial/Geometry/Height	mapping not feasible
Spatial/Geometry/Area	mapping not feasible
Spatial/Representations	mapping not feasible
Coordinates	Place/ DCTERMS Spatial
Coordinates/X	Place/ DCTERMS Spatial
Coordinates/Y	Place/ DCTERMS Spatial
Coordinates/Z	Place/ DCTERMS Spatial

Bounding Box/	mapping not feasible
Bounding Box/maxX	mapping not feasible
Bounding Box/maxY	mapping not feasible
Bounding Box/minx	mapping not feasible
Bounding Box/minY	mapping not feasible
Quickpoint	mapping not feasible
Quickpoint/X	mapping not feasible
Quickpoint/Y	mapping not feasible
Address	Place
Address/Building name	Place/ DCTERMS Title
Address/Number in road	Place/ DCTERMS Spatial
Address/Road name	Place/ DCTERMS Spatial
Address/Town or city	Place/ DCTERMS Spatial
Address/Postcode or zipcode	Place/ DCTERMS Spatial
Address/Locality	Place/ DCTERMS Spatial
Address/Admin area	Place/ DCTERMS Spatial
Address/Country	Place/ DCTERMS Country
Actors/ID	Agent/DC Identifier
Actors/Name	Agent/DC Creator -or- Agent/DC contributor -or- Agent /DC Title

Actors/ActorType	Agent -> Has Type -> Type
Actors/Roles	Agent -> Has Type -> skos:Concept
Actors/Contacts	RDFS:Resource/ -> ORE Aggregates -> ORE Aggregation -> ORE Proxy In -> ORE Proxy -> ORE Proxy For -> Europeana Object
Actors/Vital dates	Agent/DC Date
Actors/Place of birth	Agent/DC Place
Actors/Place of death	Agent/DC Place
Actors/Place of activity	Agent/DC Place
Actors/Biographical note	Agent/DC Description
Contacts	RDFS:Resource/ -> ORE Aggregates -> ORE Aggregation -> ORE Proxy In -> ORE Proxy -> ORE Proxy For -> Europeana Object
Contacts/Name	Agent/DC Contributor
Contacts/Role	skos:Concept
Contacts/Organisation	RDFS:Resource/ -> ORE Aggregates -> ORE Aggregation -> ORE Proxy In -> ORE Proxy -> ORE Proxy For -> Europeana Object
Contacts/Address	Place
Contacts/Phone	mapping not feasible
Contacts/Fax	mapping not feasible
Contacts/Email	mapping not feasible
Description	Agent/DC Description

Publication statement/Publisher	Information Resource/DC Publisher
Publication statement/Place of publication	Information Resource -> Was Present At -> Event -> Occurred At -> Place and Information Resource -> Was Present At -> Event -> Has type -> Type:=Publication
Publication statement/Date	Information Resource -> Was Present At -> Event -> Happened At -> Time Span / DC Date and Information Resource -> Was Present At -> Event -> Has type -> Type:=Publication